

Supporting Information (SI)

Calculating bond dissociation energies of X-H (X = C, N, O, S) bonds of aromatic systems via DFT: a detailed comparison of methods

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Table S1: Tested density functionals

Functional	Type ^a	X ^b	Ref.
M06-2X	HM-GGA	54	1
M05-2X	HM-GGA	56	2
M06	HM-GGA	27	1
M05	HM-GGA	28	3
BMK	M-GGA	42	4
MPW1B95	HM-GGA	31	5
B1B95	HM-GGA	25	6,7
B98	H-GGA	21.98	8
B97-2	H-GGA	21	9
LC-wPBE	H-GGA	0-100	10,11
B3LYP	H-GGA	20	12,13
cam-B3LYP	H-GGA	19-65	14
B2PLYP	H-GGA	53	15
MPWB1K	HM-GGA	44	5
BB1K	HM-GGA	42	16
BB95	M-GGA	0	6,7
M08-HX	M-GGA	52,23	17

^a M-GGA = meta generalized gradient approximation; H-GGA = hybrid generalized gradient approximation; HM-GGA = hybrid meta generalized gradient approximation

^b % of HF exchange

Table S2: Experimental values of C–H BDEs

Compound	Structure	Acronym	BDE (kcal/mol)
Benzene		CH1	112.9 ¹⁸
Toluene		CH2	88.5 ¹⁹
Ethylbenzene		CH3	85.4 ²⁰
Diphenylmethane		CH4	84.5 ²¹
Indene		CH5	83 ²²
Tetralin		CH6	82.6 ²³
Naphthalene		CH7	112.2 ²⁴
9-10-Dihydroanthracene		CH8	76.3 ²⁵
Xanthene		CH9	75.2 ²⁶
Flourene		CH10	82.0 ²⁷
9-Anthracenylmethane		CH11	84.1 ²¹

Table S3: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of C–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31+G(d) calculating models

C-H BDE	CH1	CH2	CH3	CH4	CH5	CH6	CH7	CH8	CH9	CH10	CH11
M06-2X	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
M05-2X	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
M06	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
M05	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
BMK	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
MPW1B95	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
B1B95	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
B98	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
B97-2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
LC-wPBE	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
cam-B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
B2PLYP	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
MPWB1K	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
BB1K	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
BB95	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
M08-HX	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1

Table S4: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of C–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) calculating models

C-H BDE	CH1	CH2	CH3	CH4	CH5	CH6	CH7	CH8	CH9	CH10	CH11
M06-2X	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
M05-2X	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
M06	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
M05	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
BMK	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
MPW1B95	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
B1B95	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
B98	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
B97-2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
LC-wPBE	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
cam-B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
B2PLYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
MPWB1K	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
BB1K	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
BB95	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
M08-HX	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2

Table S5: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of C–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) calculating models

C-H BDE	CH1	CH2	CH3	CH4	CH5	CH6	CH7	CH8	CH9	CH10	CH11
M06-2X	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
M05-2X	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
M06	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
M05	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
BMK	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
MPW1B95	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
B1B95	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
B98	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
B97-2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
LC-wPBE	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
cam-B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
B2PLYP	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3
MPWB1K	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
BB1K	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
BB95	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1
M08-HX	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1

Table S6: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of C–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) calculating models

C-H BDE	CH1	CH2	CH3	CH4	CH5	CH6	CH7	CH8	CH9	CH10	CH11
M06-2X	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
M05-2X	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
M06	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.2
M05	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.2
BMK	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
MPW1B95	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
B1B95	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
B98	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
B97-2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
LC-wPBE	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3
B3LYP	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
cam-B3LYP	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
B2PLYP	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3
MPWB1K	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
BB1K	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
BB95	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2
M08-HX	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2

Table S7: Experimental values of N–H BDEs

Compound	Structure	Acronym	BDE (kcal/mol)
4-Flouroaniline		NH1	88.8 ²⁸
N-methyl-N-phenylamine		NH2	89.3 ²⁹
Phenylhydrazine		NH3	72.9 ³⁰
Diphenylamine		NH4	87.2 ³¹
1,3-oxazolidin-2-one		NH5	105.8 ³²
2-piperidone		NH6	109.5 ³³
2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline		NH7	88.1 ³⁴
Carbazole		NH8	93.6 ³⁵
Dimethyl-phenothiazine		NH9	77.7 ³⁶

Table S8: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of N–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) calculating models

N-H BDE	NH1	NH2	NH3	NH4	NH5	NH6	NH7	NH8	NH9
M06-2X	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.3	0.0	0.0	-0.1
M05-2X	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.4	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1
M06	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.3	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
M05	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.6	-0.4	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
BMK	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
MPW1B95	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
B1B95	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
B98	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.6	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1
B97-2	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.6	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1
LC-wPBE	0.1	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.3	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
B3LYP	0.1	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.7	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
cam-B3LYP	0.1	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.6	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
B2PLYP	-7.1	-7.4	-7.0	-7.0	-7.9	-8.4	-7.1	-7.2	-7.1
MPWB1K	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.3	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1
BB1K	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.5	-0.3	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1
BB95	0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.7	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1
M08-HX	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.0	0.5	-0.3	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1

Table S9: Experimental values of O–H BDEs

Compound	Structure	Acronym	BDE (kcal/mol)
4-Chlorophenol		OH1	90.3 ³⁷
2-Methoxyphenol		OH2	86.2 ³⁸
4-Methoxy-2,3,6-trimethylphenol		OH3	79.2 ³⁹
2,2,5,7,8-Pentamethylchroman-6-ol		OH4	78.3 ³⁹
2,3,5-Trimethylchroman-4-ol		OH5	79.1 ³⁴
Ubiquinol-2		OH6	82.3 ³⁴
2,2,6,7-Tetramethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzofuran-5-ol		OH7	78.8 ³⁴
1-Hydroxynaphthalene		OH8	84.5 ⁴⁰

4,4'-
Dihydroxybiphe
nyl

OH9

85,2⁴⁰

1-Hydroxy-
phenanthrene

OH10

84.8³⁴

Table S10: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of O–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) calculating models

O-H BDE	OH1	OH2	OH3	OH4	OH5	OH6	OH7	OH8	OH9	OH10
M06-2X	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
M05-2X	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.3	-0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
M06	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
M05	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
BMK	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
MPW1B95	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0
B1B95	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0
B98	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
B97-2	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
LC-wPBE	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
B3LYP	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
cam-B3LYP	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
B2PLYP	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0
MPWB1K	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
BB1K	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
BB95	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0
M08-HX	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1

Table S11: Experimental values of S–H BDEs

Compound	Structure	Acronym	BDE (kcal/mol)
Benzenethiol		SH1	80.8 ³⁴
2-Methyl-benzenethiol		SH2	78.8 ⁴¹
3-Trifluoromethyl-benzenethiol		SH3	80.8 ³⁴
4-Amino-benzenethiol		SH4	69.8 ⁴¹
1-Naphthalenethiol		SH5	78.5 ³⁴
4-Chloro-benzenethiol		SH6	79.2 ⁴¹
4-Methyl-benzenethiol		SH7	78.3 ⁴¹
4-Methoxy-benzenethiol		SH8	76.9 ⁴¹
4-Ethoxy-benzenethiol		SH9	78.8 ³⁴

Table S12: Absolute (in kcal/mol) deviation of S–H BDEs of the DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) from DFT/6-311+G(3df,2p)//B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) calculating models

S-H BDE	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	SH5	SH6	SH7	SH8	SH9
M06-2X	7.7	0.0	6.9	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
M05-2X	9.0	0.0	8.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
M06	9.8	0.0	8.7	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
M05	9.3	0.1	8.4	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
BMK	9.4	0.0	8.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
MPW1B95	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
B1B95	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
B98	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
B97-2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
LC-wPBE	8.0	0.0	7.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
B3LYP	0.0	0.0	8.8	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
cam-B3LYP	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
B2PLYP	0.0	0.0	8.7	4.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
MPWB1K	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
BB1K	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
BB95	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
M08-HX	8.3	0.0	7.4	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1

Table S2: The Cartesian coordinates and energies of studied compounds at B3LYP/6-31G(d)

Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
CH1 (Benzene)					
C	-0.30703400	-1.36245600	0.00000100	Zero-point correction=	0.100751 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.02641100	-0.94712300	-0.00001600	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.105140
C	1.33344400	0.41532900	0.00000900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.106085
C	0.30702900	1.36245800	-0.00000300	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.073288
C	-1.02640900	0.94712700	-0.00000800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-232.147900
C	-1.33344200	-0.41533300	0.00001100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-232.143510
H	-0.54590800	-2.42246200	-0.00000300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-232.142566
H	1.82495400	-1.68400500	0.00001200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-232.175363
H	2.37086900	0.73845600	0.00002200		
H	0.54591100	2.42245700	0.00001600		
H	-1.82495300	1.68399600	-0.00002200		
H	-2.37087400	-0.73845500	0.00001800		
CH1-RAD (Benzene)					
C	-1.21412800	0.63262500	0.00000000	Zero-point correction=	0.087618 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.22625100	-0.77176600	0.00000200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.091987
C	-0.00001000	-1.40033100	-0.00000200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.092931
C	1.22624800	-0.77177300	0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.059575
C	1.21413400	0.63261400	0.00000000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-231.473658
C	0.00000400	1.32474600	0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-231.469289
H	-2.15453500	1.17915500	-0.00000200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-231.468345
H	-2.16283900	-1.32317200	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-231.501700
H	2.16282900	-1.32319000	0.00000100		
H	2.15454500	1.17913900	-0.00000100		
H	0.00000900	2.41138000	-0.00000300		
CH2 (Toluene)					
C	-1.20119500	1.20542000	0.00216100	Zero-point correction=	0.128291 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.19427300	1.20237500	-0.00885200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.134516
C	0.91390900	-0.00001000	-0.01112400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.135460
C	0.19426300	-1.20238000	-0.00885100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.097398
C	-1.20121200	-1.20541100	0.00216000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-271.438347
C	-1.90504900	0.00000600	0.00840100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-271.432122
H	-1.73853600	2.15045900	0.00137900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-271.431178
H	0.73436500	2.14690300	-0.01761200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-271.469240
H	0.73434300	-2.14691300	-0.01761000		
H	-1.73856000	-2.15044600	0.00137600		
H	-2.99180200	0.00001400	0.01366800		
C	2.42541200	-0.00000400	0.00919800		
H	2.81037200	0.00068800	1.03798500		
H	2.83369000	-0.88635100	-0.48827500		
H	2.83371900	0.88567200	-0.48947000		
CH2-RAD (Toluene)					
C	-1.13382400	1.21204200	-0.00002700	Zero-point correction=	0.114949 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.25199500	1.21824400	0.00030200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.120616
C	0.99539300	-0.00001900	0.00014400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.121560
C	0.25196500	-1.21827800	0.00039200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.085281
C	-1.13383200	-1.21203200	-0.00004800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-270.800189
C	-1.83975400	0.00002800	-0.00030000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-270.794522
H	-1.67669400	2.15386500	-0.00002900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-270.793578
H	0.79398500	2.16087800	0.00049900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-270.829857
H	0.79393400	-2.16092400	0.00070200		

H	-1.67673900	-2.15383400	-0.00007800		
H	-2.92604400	0.00003200	-0.00058700		
C	2.40192600	0.00001100	-0.00034600		
H	2.96414300	-0.92811600	-0.00105700		
H	2.96419900	0.92812300	-0.00015400		
CH3 (Ethylbenzene)					
C	1.63700900	1.20600600	0.09580400	Zero-point correction=	0.157372 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.27012100	1.20257200	-0.18533400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.164695
C	-0.43490000	-0.00017400	-0.32866000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.165639
C	0.27037600	-1.20272600	-0.18511500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.125153
C	1.63727600	-1.20581100	0.09603900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-310.722856
C	2.32590900	0.00018000	0.23824500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-310.715532
H	2.16491600	2.15076400	0.19877900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-310.714588
H	-0.25848500	2.14695800	-0.29991400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-310.755075
H	-0.25802300	-2.14724400	-0.29954600		
H	2.16538300	-2.15043900	0.19918500		
H	3.39116000	0.00031900	0.45356100		
C	-1.92657400	-0.00033400	-0.59203700		
H	-2.19350900	0.87846500	-1.19280100		
H	-2.19340100	-0.87979800	-1.19187700		
C	-2.76221400	0.00025200	0.70081400		
H	-2.54278700	0.88486800	1.30924100		
H	-3.83487300	-0.00009000	0.47459100		
H	-2.54239900	-0.88359200	1.31024400		
CH3-RAD (Ethylbenzene)					
C	1.33803600	1.36583000	0.00000100	Zero-point correction=	0.143164 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.01528300	1.05781900	0.00002300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.150630
C	-0.46152500	-0.29569400	0.00002000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.151574
C	0.54093800	-1.30944400	-0.00000600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.110388
C	1.88959600	-0.99087700	-0.00001200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-310.090185
C	2.30219300	0.34944900	-0.00001000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-310.082719
H	1.65087100	2.40712200	-0.00000400	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-310.081775
H	-0.74755400	1.85987200	0.00002800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-310.122960
H	0.22818500	-2.35122900	-0.00000700		
H	2.63098400	-1.78601000	-0.00001800		
H	3.35986000	0.59736100	-0.00001600		
C	-1.83301100	-0.64662500	0.00002500		
H	-2.07618300	-1.70662500	0.00005500		
C	-2.96575400	0.33241300	-0.00003000		
H	-2.94313200	0.99192900	-0.88083700		
H	-3.93112700	-0.18175000	0.00007700		
H	-2.94304300	0.99210000	0.88064800		
CH4 (Diphenylmethane)					
C	-0.00032800	-0.15232600	1.43731100	Zero-point correction=	0.210309 (Hartree/Particle)
H	-0.04661700	-1.09223900	2.00329700	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.220633
H	0.04547100	0.64822600	2.18762500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.221577
C	-3.47650900	-0.83287000	-0.02020400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.171940
C	-2.29200400	-0.97260800	0.70771600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-502.405056
C	-1.27919800	-0.01035100	0.62663900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-502.394732
C	-1.47858900	1.09947400	-0.20764600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-502.393788
C	-2.65898000	1.24386300	-0.93434700	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-502.443425
C	-3.66398000	0.27683900	-0.84328400		
H	-4.24994200	-1.59281800	0.05702900		
H	-2.15409900	-1.83990200	1.35006200		
H	-0.69694600	1.85085900	-0.29119800		

H	-2.79529300	2.11179900	-1.57453800	
H	-4.58379400	0.38868800	-1.41119500	
C	2.28892400	0.80678900	0.89278100	
C	3.47364700	0.82286700	0.15206500	
C	3.66425900	-0.09393400	-0.88098100	
C	2.66220900	-1.02483800	-1.16871800	
C	1.48157700	-1.03605300	-0.42828500	
C	1.27902000	-0.12143800	0.61573700	
H	2.14858400	1.52346600	1.69931800	
H	4.24481700	1.55313400	0.38377500	
H	4.58427300	-0.08420000	-1.45940300	
H	2.80103800	-1.74271500	-1.97315300	
H	0.70222800	-1.75678600	-0.66431800	
CH4-RAD (Diphenylmethane)				
C	-0.00000400	-1.03900400	0.00015300	Zero-point correction= 0.197415 (Hartree/Particle)
H	0.00005200	-2.12820000	0.00001400	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.207472
C	-3.71595100	-0.74187900	-0.29542900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.208416
C	-2.42485200	-1.25032100	-0.29930200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.160380
C	-1.30314900	-0.43852700	0.02173900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -501.781422
C	-1.56699200	0.90717700	0.39180100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -501.771365
C	-2.86359500	1.40808600	0.39950800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -501.770421
C	-3.94652800	0.59585100	0.04703500	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -501.818458
H	-4.54978100	-1.38797000	-0.55775300	
H	-2.25492100	-2.29040900	-0.56773200	
H	-0.75249300	1.54205000	0.72071100	
H	-3.03467000	2.43966500	0.69677100	
H	-4.95696800	0.99479300	0.05326800	
C	2.42489300	-1.25028900	0.29931900	
C	3.71600900	-0.74187800	0.29512800	
C	3.94653200	0.59585200	-0.04734100	
C	2.86354000	1.40812800	-0.39953600	
C	1.56693100	0.90724600	-0.39153000	
C	1.30315900	-0.43845800	-0.02142300	
H	2.25502400	-2.29040200	0.56772400	
H	4.54989100	-1.38800600	0.55719600	
H	4.95698300	0.99476300	-0.05381500	
H	3.03457500	2.43970500	-0.69682800	
H	0.75235000	1.54210000	-0.72029700	
CH5 (Indene)				
C	0.23015000	-0.68976600	0.00001000	Zero-point correction= 0.140905 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.21195300	0.72281600	-0.00002100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.147279
C	-0.99995600	1.41564300	-0.00002900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.148224
C	-2.19143300	0.68443500	-0.00001100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.110441
C	-2.17220200	-0.71398200	0.00003000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -347.621947
C	-0.95639000	-1.41084900	0.00003600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -347.615572
C	1.66970400	-1.15588100	-0.00004900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -347.614628
C	2.44083400	0.14448700	0.00009500	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -347.652410
C	1.59994600	1.19704200	0.00001800	
H	-1.02044700	2.50275100	-0.00003500	
H	-3.14383700	1.20828600	-0.00001500	
H	-3.10863400	-1.26550700	0.00005100	
H	-0.94966600	-2.49864200	0.00006200	
H	1.88639800	2.24402800	0.00000600	
H	3.52432600	0.19233900	0.00018000	
H	1.90806900	-1.77306100	-0.87903600	

H	1.90816500	-1.77386100	0.87831400	
CH5-RAD (Indene)				
C	0.25862400	-0.71527700	0.00029900	Zero-point correction= 0.128041 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.25875300	0.71536500	0.00033200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.134276
C	-0.94034100	1.41713200	-0.00013800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.135220
C	-2.14962900	0.69730100	-0.00003000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.097121
C	-2.14972400	-0.69726900	0.00000400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -347.001671
C	-0.94045300	-1.41728800	-0.00004400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -346.995437
C	1.64808600	-1.14113600	-0.00031700	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -346.994493
C	2.46173700	0.00008000	0.00008100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -347.032592
C	1.64760800	1.14099800	0.00002200	
H	-0.95181700	2.50454400	-0.00070400	
H	-3.09326800	1.23593200	-0.00002900	
H	-3.09341200	-1.23582100	0.00009800	
H	-0.95201600	-2.50468500	-0.00008600	
H	1.98838200	2.17042800	-0.00019800	
H	3.54503600	0.00059000	-0.00005700	
H	1.98912200	-2.17042300	-0.00028200	
CH6 (Tetralin)				
C	2.52993100	-0.69773400	-0.19907300	Zero-point correction= 0.194517 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.33624100	-1.39331400	0.00772600	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.202543
C	0.14106900	-0.70394900	0.22380000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.203487
C	0.14110600	0.70392700	0.22398000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.161439
C	1.33632300	1.39326400	0.00806500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -388.108190
C	2.52997800	0.69766100	-0.19889600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -388.100165
H	3.45479700	-1.24427900	-0.36465800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -388.099220
H	1.33332200	-2.48150400	0.00108900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -388.141269
C	-1.18671000	-1.38585500	0.45006000	
C	-1.18676900	1.38582800	0.44995500	
H	1.33345100	2.48145500	0.00164600	
H	3.45487900	1.24418500	-0.36435300	
C	-2.28718600	0.77867200	-0.45149500	
C	-2.28776900	-0.77849700	-0.45098700	
H	-1.10715700	2.46511300	0.27578000	
H	-1.48409300	1.26458700	1.50304900	
H	-2.13177200	1.14124900	-1.47397600	
H	-3.26294500	1.16305200	-0.13236800	
H	-3.26346000	-1.16198800	-0.13069000	
H	-2.13350100	-1.14191600	-1.47334000	
H	-1.10722700	-2.46509600	0.27570000	
H	-1.48358500	-1.26486400	1.50331700	
CH6-RAD (Tetralin)				
C	-2.54200800	0.71090300	-0.05337400	Zero-point correction= 0.180607 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.31832900	1.38711100	0.03462400	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.188440
C	-0.11153800	0.70007200	0.09642800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.189384
C	-0.11421100	-0.73384300	0.05358900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.147693
C	-1.37081400	-1.40049900	-0.03195600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -387.482285
C	-2.55916000	-0.69115500	-0.08295100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -387.474453
H	-3.47126300	1.27178500	-0.09998100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -387.473508
H	-1.30796300	2.47527500	0.05913700	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -387.515200
C	1.21132700	1.42310200	0.23642500	
C	1.09817500	-1.45527500	0.09266000	
H	-1.38098200	-2.48780400	-0.06179300	
H	-3.50521000	-1.22231200	-0.14975300	
C	2.43787700	-0.78276200	0.11097500	

C	2.35791400	0.65270200	-0.43471900		
H	1.05866600	-2.54225500	0.11076300		
H	3.16510800	-1.37250300	-0.46407600		
H	2.83454200	-0.75792400	1.14241300		
H	3.30986100	1.17354800	-0.27817100		
H	2.18310100	0.61710500	-1.51791100		
H	1.13114000	2.43613400	-0.17660800		
H	1.44759700	1.54681500	1.30577100		
CH7 (Naphthalene)					
C	2.43347500	-0.70849300	0.00000600	Zero-point correction=	0.147818 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.24468000	-1.40245300	-0.00001200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.154627
C	-0.00000500	-0.71652800	-0.00000400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.155571
C	0.00001000	0.71654100	-0.00001000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.116615
C	1.24469900	1.40245800	-0.00000400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-385.744887
C	2.43349200	0.70846900	0.00001400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-385.738079
H	-1.24174500	-2.48973800	-0.00002200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-385.737134
H	3.37792000	-1.24517700	0.00000600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-385.776091
H	1.24172300	-2.48974000	-0.00001300		
C	-1.24469600	-1.40244900	0.00000300		
C	-1.24468700	1.40245000	-0.00001100		
H	1.24176400	2.48975300	0.00001100		
H	3.37794600	1.24514400	0.00002000		
C	-2.43348000	0.70848700	0.00000000		
C	-2.43348800	-0.70848100	0.00001400		
H	-1.24174000	2.48973600	-0.00001700		
H	-3.37792600	1.24517300	0.00002800		
H	-3.37794100	-1.24515800	0.00001700		
CH7-RAD (Naphthalene)					
C	2.44033400	-0.68651200	-0.00000100	Zero-point correction=	0.134842 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.27451600	-1.41857400	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.141627
C	0.01418200	-0.76276300	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.142571
C	-0.03546400	0.67849700	0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.103015
C	1.19200100	1.39360900	0.00000000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-385.070219
C	2.39841000	0.72977300	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-385.063434
H	3.40083000	-1.19451900	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-385.062490
H	1.29737700	-2.50442500	0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-385.102046
C	-1.22807700	-1.41327500	0.00000100		
C	-1.30282900	1.32513700	0.00000000		
H	1.16225000	2.48095100	-0.00000100		
H	3.32765200	1.29311100	-0.00000100		
C	-2.47693600	0.60547500	0.00000000		
C	-2.45058700	-0.82081900	-0.00000100		
H	-1.32997100	2.41210200	0.00000100		
H	-3.43504800	1.11955200	-0.00000100		
H	-3.37638500	-1.39006200	-0.00000200		
CH8 (9-10-Dihydroanthracene)					
C	3.56676700	-0.69784700	-0.49681800	Zero-point correction=	0.217566 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.41415200	-1.39005100	-0.12396200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.227575
C	1.25913100	-0.70219700	0.25964700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.228519
C	1.25917400	0.70217300	0.25974900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.181847
C	2.41428400	1.38999300	-0.12367200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-540.517534
C	3.56684100	0.69776000	-0.49665800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-540.507525
C	-0.00001900	-1.43218400	0.68476000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-540.506581
C	0.00001000	1.43227800	0.68467800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-540.553253
C	-1.25914600	0.70220600	0.25968900		

C	-1.25917500	-0.70215600	0.25978200	
C	-2.41425100	-1.39001500	-0.12366700	
H	-2.40897700	-2.47802800	-0.13260600	
C	-3.56681500	-0.69780500	-0.49668000	
C	-3.56677700	0.69780400	-0.49682900	
C	-2.41418100	1.39003400	-0.12394800	
H	4.45703600	-1.24586600	-0.79388300	
H	2.40879800	-2.47806400	-0.13312900	
H	2.40903200	2.47800800	-0.13261600	
H	4.45717500	1.24575500	-0.79357200	
H	-4.45713000	-1.24581900	-0.79361400	
H	-4.45705500	1.24580300	-0.79390400	
H	-2.40884700	2.47804700	-0.13312500	
H	-0.00001500	1.53445500	1.78345900	
H	0.00005200	2.45539800	0.29141800	
H	0.00003900	-1.53430400	1.78354500	
H	-0.00008500	-2.45534400	0.29159700	
CH8-RAD (9-10-Dihydroanthracene)				
C	3.71781500	-0.64493300	-0.00002000	Zero-point correction= 0.204082 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.51772100	-1.35965300	-0.00000600	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.214192
C	1.28473700	-0.70881600	0.00000800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.215136
C	1.24956400	0.71367800	0.00001100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.166378
C	2.47689900	1.42379600	-0.00000600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -539.901420
C	3.69142200	0.75639600	-0.00002100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -539.891310
C	-0.00000300	-1.51240300	0.00003700	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -539.890365
C	0.00000100	1.39712800	0.00002200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -539.939124
C	-1.24956500	0.71367900	0.00002000	
C	-1.28473600	-0.70881500	0.00001300	
C	-2.51772000	-1.35965200	-0.00001400	
H	-2.54196400	-2.44800000	-0.00002300	
C	-3.71781500	-0.64493300	-0.00002800	
C	-3.69142100	0.75639600	-0.00001700	
C	-2.47689900	1.42379700	0.00000600	
H	4.66605500	-1.17517900	-0.00003100	
H	2.54196500	-2.44800000	-0.00000600	
H	2.44947800	2.51104600	-0.00000500	
H	4.62094900	1.31950200	-0.00003300	
H	-4.66605400	-1.17517900	-0.00004800	
H	-4.62094900	1.31950100	-0.00002800	
H	-2.44947800	2.51104600	0.00001000	
H	0.00000000	2.48443000	0.00001700	
H	-0.00000600	-2.18655100	0.87109400	
H	-0.00000400	-2.18660100	-0.87097900	
CH9 (Xanthece)				
C	3.58202400	-0.81638900	0.13390900	Zero-point correction= 0.193028 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.33879000	-1.42853500	0.00965500	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.202904
C	1.18847000	-0.64153900	-0.08954100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.203848
C	1.25517900	0.75533400	-0.07032300	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.156745
C	2.51671000	1.34633600	0.06652100	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -576.442326
C	3.67487100	0.57817100	0.16672600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -576.432450
C	0.00000000	1.58562200	-0.22594700	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -576.431506
C	-1.25517900	0.75533400	-0.07032400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -576.478609
C	-1.18847000	-0.64153900	-0.08954100	
C	-2.33879100	-1.42853500	0.00965500	
H	-2.23371500	-2.50873800	-0.00875200	

C	-3.58202400	-0.81638900	0.13391000	
C	-3.67487000	0.57817100	0.16672500	
C	-2.51671000	1.34633600	0.06652000	
H	4.47669000	-1.42798700	0.21082400	
H	2.23371400	-2.50873800	-0.00875200	
H	2.58407200	2.43219800	0.08887600	
H	4.64184500	1.06200000	0.26952500	
H	-4.47669000	-1.42798700	0.21082500	
H	-4.64184500	1.06200000	0.26952400	
H	-2.58407100	2.43219800	0.08887400	
H	-0.00000200	2.40717200	0.50347900	
H	-0.00000100	2.07078700	-1.21506800	
O	0.00000000	-1.32839800	-0.20712800	
CH9-RAD (Xanthece)				
C	3.59583500	-0.77051500	-0.00029700	Zero-point correction= 0.180064 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.35369400	-1.40882600	-0.00013300	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.189684
C	1.19330700	-0.64461900	0.00014900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.190628
C	1.22795600	0.77520500	0.00019600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.144365
C	2.50476400	1.38842600	0.00001300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -575.830511
C	3.66668300	0.62989400	-0.00020900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -575.820891
C	0.00000100	1.48713600	0.00015400	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -575.819947
C	-1.22795900	0.77521500	0.00018000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -575.866210
C	-1.19329500	-0.64461600	0.00010400	
C	-2.35367700	-1.40882600	-0.00017600	
H	-2.26907100	-2.49091700	-0.00027700	
C	-3.59582600	-0.77053200	-0.00030800	
C	-3.66668500	0.62987800	-0.00018000	
C	-2.50477800	1.38842500	0.00004000	
H	4.50483200	-1.36461800	-0.00053200	
H	2.26909900	-2.49091700	-0.00021600	
H	2.55618000	2.47431000	0.00002200	
H	4.63418700	1.12395100	-0.00035700	
H	-4.50481800	-1.36464200	-0.00053800	
H	-4.63419400	1.12392800	-0.00029900	
H	-2.55620400	2.47430800	0.00007900	
H	-0.00012700	2.57294000	-0.00056200	
O	-0.00000100	-1.32697500	0.00068600	
CH10 (Flourene)				
H	-0.00003700	2.49221000	-0.87947000	Zero-point correction= 0.188437 (Hartree/Particle)
C	3.01634900	-1.21197600	-0.00014200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.197343
C	3.46177900	0.11449700	-0.00014200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.198287
C	2.54532800	1.17226000	-0.00008900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.154350
C	1.18473300	0.88689800	-0.00003700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -501.234752
C	0.73477900	-0.45018800	-0.00003700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -501.225846
C	1.65095500	-1.50437800	-0.00009000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -501.224902
H	3.74029500	-2.02261800	-0.00018400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -501.268838
H	4.52791900	0.32511200	-0.00018200	
H	2.89787400	2.20121700	-0.00009000	
H	1.31173400	-2.53721900	-0.00008900	
C	0.00000000	1.83287600	0.00002500	
H	0.00003700	2.49218600	0.87953900	
C	-1.18473300	0.88689800	0.00006200	
C	-2.54532800	1.17226000	0.00012300	
C	-3.46177900	0.11449700	0.00014600	
C	-3.01635000	-1.21197600	0.00010700	

C	-1.65095500	-1.50437800	0.00004700		
C	-0.73477900	-0.45018800	0.00002400		
H	-2.89787400	2.20121700	0.00015100		
H	-4.52791900	0.32511200	0.00019400		
H	-3.74029500	-2.02261800	0.00012600		
H	-1.31173400	-2.53721900	0.00001800		
CH10-RAD (Flourene)					
H	0.00000000	2.83046200	0.00077700	Zero-point correction=	0.175508 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-3.03511500	-1.16085500	0.00001500	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.184273
C	-3.45903200	0.17496400	-0.00003900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.185217
C	-2.53058000	1.21731400	-0.00010200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.140998
C	-1.16192900	0.90892800	-0.00012900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-500.611717
C	-0.73409100	-0.45929600	0.00000000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-500.602953
C	-1.66879600	-1.48465200	0.00005600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-500.602008
H	-3.77356200	-1.95800400	0.00003200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-500.646228
H	-4.52199300	0.40022300	-0.00004000		
H	-2.86341400	2.25232300	-0.00012300		
H	-1.35717600	-2.52637200	0.00006900		
C	0.00000000	1.74605800	0.00029100		
C	1.16192900	0.90892800	-0.00012900		
C	2.53058000	1.21731400	-0.00010200		
C	3.45903200	0.17496400	-0.00003900		
C	3.03511500	-1.16085500	0.00001500		
C	1.66879600	-1.48465200	0.00005600		
C	0.73409100	-0.45929600	0.00000000		
H	2.86341400	2.25232300	-0.00012300		
H	4.52199300	0.40022300	-0.00004000		
H	3.77356200	-1.95800400	0.00003200		
H	1.35717600	-2.52637200	0.00006900		
CH11 (9-Anthracenylmethane)					
C	3.66838100	0.41801400	-0.00000500	Zero-point correction=	0.222471 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.49938400	1.13534400	-0.00000700	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.233719
C	1.22152100	0.48722500	0.00000600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.234663
C	1.21015600	-0.95668900	0.00000900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.184943
C	2.44994200	-1.66817900	0.00001200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-578.619626
C	3.64756400	-1.00483000	0.00000700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-578.608378
C	0.00286400	1.21043900	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-578.607434
C	-0.01390700	-1.63069300	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-578.657153
C	-1.22666700	-0.93920500	-0.00000900		
C	-1.22817500	0.51058100	-0.00000400		
C	-2.50992300	1.15622200	0.00001900		
H	-2.56650400	2.23832700	0.00005200		
C	-3.67949000	0.44245000	0.00001400		
C	-3.66564400	-0.98106300	-0.00000900		
C	-2.47068800	-1.64586600	-0.00001800		
H	4.62220200	0.93897500	-0.00001500		
H	2.54604000	2.21862000	-0.00002000		
H	2.41836700	-2.75530800	0.00001800		
H	4.58295500	-1.55778400	0.00000900		
H	-0.02270700	-2.71880500	-0.00000600		
H	-4.63078900	0.96796200	0.00003400		
H	-4.60302600	-1.53054600	-0.00001500		
H	-2.44076100	-2.73302400	-0.00002700		
C	0.06412700	2.72347700	-0.00001200		
H	0.59847200	3.09841000	0.88170700		

H	0.59846700	3.09839500	-0.88172300		
H	-0.91939100	3.19141100	-0.00002500		
CH11-RAD (9-Anthracenylmethane)					
C	-3.70081100	0.43929500	-0.11665200	Zero-point correction=	0.209139 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-2.52149800	1.16607400	-0.09526200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.219955
C	-1.26129300	0.53846200	-0.00092100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.220899
C	-1.23436200	-0.89338000	0.04777900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.171543
C	-2.45912400	-1.61720800	0.03428300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-577.991626
C	-3.67134300	-0.96787200	-0.04348600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-577.980810
C	0.00000000	1.29647700	0.05620000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-577.979866
C	0.00000100	-1.57589500	0.09664200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-578.029222
C	1.23436300	-0.89337800	0.04779000		
C	1.26129300	0.53846300	-0.00092100		
C	2.52149700	1.16607500	-0.09528500		
H	2.58173300	2.24634800	-0.16928700		
C	3.70081100	0.43929500	-0.11666600		
C	3.67134400	-0.96787000	-0.04347100		
C	2.45912600	-1.61720600	0.03430600		
H	-4.65160500	0.95925800	-0.19461000		
H	-2.58173800	2.24635000	-0.16922400		
H	-2.41670200	-2.70287700	0.07930700		
H	-4.59828500	-1.53464900	-0.05690600		
H	0.00000100	-2.66235300	0.14231300		
H	4.65160400	0.95925800	-0.19464600		
H	4.59828700	-1.53464700	-0.05688300		
H	2.41670500	-2.70287400	0.07934600		
C	-0.00000200	2.65883300	0.19523600		
H	-0.91455300	3.23260100	0.27155200		
H	0.91454800	3.23259300	0.27161100		
NH1 (4-Flouroaniline)					
C	-0.72824500	-1.21073300	0.00085000	Zero-point correction=	0.109171 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.66537300	-1.20738800	0.00610000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.115784
C	1.38429100	-0.00018500	0.00867000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.116728
C	0.66568000	1.20706400	0.00610000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.078663
C	-0.72804500	1.21072400	0.00087900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-386.724326
C	-1.40920100	0.00010900	-0.00171500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-386.717712
H	-1.28744100	-2.14092800	-0.00304800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-386.716768
H	1.20370500	-2.15235200	0.01371600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-386.754833
H	1.20426400	2.15187800	0.01378400		
H	-1.28700200	2.14106000	-0.00293200		
N	2.78570400	0.00015700	0.07785400		
H	3.22119600	-0.83283000	-0.30026000		
H	3.22114400	0.83287800	-0.30102000		
F	-2.76387900	0.00018300	-0.01005800		
NH1-RAD (4-Flouroaniline)					
C	0.65580800	-1.22656700	0.00005100	Zero-point correction=	0.095895 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.72661200	-1.21442500	0.00009700	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.102060
C	-1.46284200	0.01859200	-0.00010700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.103004
C	-0.70382900	1.23708300	0.00007300	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.065034
C	0.67717000	1.22522600	0.00002600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-386.091659
C	1.34063600	-0.00692100	-0.00001600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-386.085494
H	1.22178700	-2.15262000	0.00006300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-386.084550
H	-1.27769800	-2.15191000	0.00023100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-386.122520
H	-1.25967900	2.16898400	0.00007900		
H	1.25947200	2.14098800	0.00002400		

N	-2.79879100	0.11528200	0.00005600		
H	-3.20375500	-0.82945400	-0.00086800		
F	2.68549200	-0.02009900	-0.00007400		
NH2 (N-methyl-phenylamine)					
C	1.87848700	0.99572700	0.04409600	Zero-point correction=	0.145886 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.52291700	1.29844500	-0.00658800	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.153093
C	-0.44370100	0.27369800	-0.06110600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.154037
C	-0.00121700	-1.06164700	-0.05751800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.114601
C	1.36355700	-1.35108300	-0.01157800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-326.763731
C	2.31458100	-0.33317100	0.04078800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-326.756525
H	2.60177000	1.80646400	0.08717800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-326.755581
H	0.19625100	2.33684900	-0.01089200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-326.795017
H	-0.71867200	-1.87478200	-0.09249300		
H	1.68066300	-2.39123800	-0.01127800		
H	3.37439300	-0.56699500	0.08011800		
N	-1.79279700	0.60949800	-0.15211600		
H	-2.00168000	1.54123100	0.18035000		
C	-2.83518800	-0.36462300	0.10855500		
H	-2.73864700	-0.86172500	1.08809000		
H	-3.80373200	0.14075000	0.06898900		
H	-2.83739000	-1.14110300	-0.66514300		
NH2-RAD (N-methyl-phenylamine)					
C	1.29380800	1.36564300	0.00001000	Zero-point correction=	0.131865 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.05944000	1.06481800	-0.00008300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.138919
C	-0.50377300	-0.29540100	-0.00011100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.139863
C	0.49859200	-1.31512700	-0.00000600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.099947
C	1.84616300	-0.99939900	0.00003300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-326.133509
C	2.25444600	0.34318600	0.00002600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-326.126455
H	1.61418900	2.40448900	0.00008300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-326.125511
H	-0.78704900	1.86960700	0.00001000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-326.165427
H	0.15356300	-2.34439300	-0.00002400		
H	2.58982700	-1.79182200	0.00006600		
H	3.31201800	0.59192400	0.00006600		
N	-1.78568200	-0.72014700	0.00001500		
C	-2.83151100	0.28011300	0.00006800		
H	-2.78426400	0.93373700	-0.88598500		
H	-3.80430700	-0.21983000	0.00041000		
H	-2.78391800	0.93432500	0.88564600		
NH3 (Phenylhydrazine)					
C	-2.30673700	0.30605400	0.05519100	Zero-point correction=	0.134721 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.84918200	-1.01356100	0.06159400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.141683
C	-0.48606000	-1.29124400	-0.00253100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.142627
C	0.45009200	-0.24624400	-0.08302600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.103652
C	-0.00710400	1.08022200	-0.08666500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-342.779148
C	-1.37456900	1.34312900	-0.01845200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-342.772185
H	-3.37001800	0.52120200	0.10943900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-342.771241
H	-2.55675800	-1.83678000	0.12305400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-342.810217
H	-0.13983000	-2.32355400	0.00354300		
H	0.71791100	1.88360300	-0.14159000		
H	-1.71313600	2.37654100	-0.02164500		
N	1.81338600	-0.56431900	-0.21199100		
H	2.03108200	-1.49580100	0.13452800		
N	2.74106400	0.43835900	0.14772600		
H	3.02676600	0.35075500	1.12502100		
H	3.56419600	0.33561500	-0.43915900		

NH3-RAD (Phenylhydrazine)					
C	2.24347300	0.31050800	0.05384500	Zero-point correction=	0.121740 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.80192800	-1.02012500	0.05132400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.128349
C	0.44745300	-1.30930300	-0.01328100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.129293
C	-0.51601000	-0.27029400	-0.06240600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.090495
C	-0.05570700	1.07198400	-0.07896300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-342.171398
C	1.30702300	1.34635700	-0.02046000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-342.164790
H	3.30518700	0.53561800	0.09962300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-342.163845
H	2.52369500	-1.83145500	0.09784200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-342.202643
H	0.08646600	-2.33328100	-0.01472100		
H	-0.75912100	1.89135300	-0.19234800		
H	1.64452700	2.37961400	-0.04554800		
N	-1.82966200	-0.67174500	-0.09494600		
N	-2.74123900	0.32117500	0.03753800		
H	-3.66503600	-0.05634400	0.21263900		
H	-2.50837900	1.09371400	0.66401900		
NH4 (Diphenylamine)					
C	-1.26700800	-0.43979500	-0.01892100	Zero-point correction=	0.198376 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.50014700	0.85288700	-0.52077300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.208672
C	-2.79368800	1.37237400	-0.54257200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.209616
C	-3.87956600	0.62212800	-0.08861200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.161371
C	-3.65365900	-0.66984800	0.39153900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-518.453421
C	-2.36505500	-1.19390800	0.43431500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-518.443126
C	1.50024400	0.85279400	0.52102400	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-518.442182
C	2.79377700	1.37230700	0.54259400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-518.490426
C	3.87956000	0.62210600	0.08833400		
C	3.65357400	-0.66984300	-0.39185100		
C	2.36497300	-1.19393300	-0.43438200		
C	1.26700800	-0.43984600	0.01910100		
H	-0.67632500	1.43651500	-0.91561000		
H	-2.95149500	2.37351700	-0.93585900		
H	-4.88397500	1.03436100	-0.11215400		
H	-4.48480800	-1.27394000	0.74632900		
H	-2.19652800	-2.19441000	0.82754400		
H	2.95166500	2.37342200	0.93592500		
H	4.88396700	1.03435400	0.11167800		
H	4.48466100	-1.27389700	-0.74684900		
H	2.19639300	-2.19442700	-0.82760300		
N	-0.00000400	-1.03328700	0.00021900		
H	-0.00005600	-2.04337100	0.00023100		
H	0.67646300	1.43635200	0.91605400		
NH4-RAD (Diphenylamine)					
C	-1.20235300	-0.48249900	-0.02635300	Zero-point correction=	0.185202 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.43293300	0.81054800	-0.57501400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.195077
C	-2.71490200	1.34524900	-0.60810900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.196021
C	-3.80050700	0.63020800	-0.08914400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.148367
C	-3.59685100	-0.65177800	0.43903700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-517.829130
C	-2.32743000	-1.20942000	0.44993100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-517.819255
C	1.43314500	0.81052400	0.57555300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-517.818311
C	2.71512100	1.34518300	0.60804300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-517.865965
C	3.80050900	0.63009200	0.08863800		
C	3.59663500	-0.65189300	-0.43948200		
C	2.32720200	-1.20946500	-0.44988800		
C	1.20232700	-0.48252200	0.02692800		
H	-0.60567700	1.35641200	-1.01587200		

H	-2.87438300	2.32587900	-1.04929300	
H	-4.79827300	1.05925900	-0.11371500	
H	-4.43860000	-1.21810300	0.82871400	
H	-2.15114500	-2.20739600	0.83891700	
H	2.87481600	2.32584600	1.04907200	
H	4.79828400	1.05914400	0.11278700	
H	4.43821900	-1.21821100	-0.82952600	
H	2.15063700	-2.20738400	-0.83889100	
N	0.00004000	-1.13391100	0.00006300	
H	0.60607600	1.35656900	1.01653400	
NH5 (1,3-oxazolidin-2-one)				
C	0.86288100	-0.00669100	0.01331500	Zero-point correction= 0.088067 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.02790700	1.08409700	0.18622900	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.093049
H	0.42081400	1.98984500	-0.02879200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.093993
O	2.06670200	-0.02094900	-0.03586400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.059674
O	0.08135500	-1.13147000	-0.08421600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -322.448926
C	-1.34376100	0.74382500	-0.15311800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -322.443945
H	-1.58514500	0.96758400	-1.20280100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -322.443000
H	-2.06849600	1.25304500	0.48933700	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -322.477319
C	-1.29568900	-0.77272600	0.11176500	
H	-1.90893000	-1.35744000	-0.57654500	
H	-1.57863300	-1.00881300	1.14407700	
NH5-RAD (1,3-oxazolidin-2-one)				
C	0.85534800	0.03890300	0.00061300	Zero-point correction= 0.072841 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.06073200	1.20493400	0.00438200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.077214
O	2.06235600	0.01908100	-0.00089200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.078159
O	0.09391800	-1.10314900	-0.00215400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.044152
C	-1.31083800	0.77447800	-0.00350900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -321.793419
H	-1.80907300	1.20214300	-0.88678900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -321.789046
H	-1.82399500	1.21082900	0.86646500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -321.788102
C	-1.29772200	-0.77302800	0.00283900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -321.822108
H	-1.76557800	-1.21289400	-0.88306000	
H	-1.75740100	-1.20417900	0.89741700	
NH6 (2-piperidone)				
C	1.15304300	-0.01853200	0.00727500	Zero-point correction= 0.140741 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.40122300	-1.15925100	-0.11423600	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.147395
H	0.91204000	-2.00690700	-0.32511800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.148340
O	2.34961300	0.02047000	-0.24356000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.109279
C	-0.98160200	-1.22080700	0.34378200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -325.800323
H	-1.03131500	-1.16761300	1.44265000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -325.793669
H	-1.39807900	-2.19030100	0.05526600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -325.792725
C	-1.79801700	-0.07458300	-0.27802200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -325.831785
H	-2.75252400	0.00473300	0.25499800	
H	-2.03424300	-0.33875400	-1.31433000	
C	-1.02697300	1.27554200	-0.24906500	
H	-1.63221800	2.05564000	0.22543700	
H	-0.84546100	1.61098100	-1.27587400	
C	0.33213200	1.17742300	0.47609000	
H	0.93469500	2.07615100	0.32575300	
H	0.17014800	1.07281300	1.55898400	
NH6-RAD (2-piperidone)				
C	-1.11914800	-0.03694700	0.03685000	Zero-point correction= 0.125566 (Hartree/Particle)
N	-0.44649600	-1.19076200	0.41264000	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.132098
O	-2.30201200	-0.11226900	-0.28212100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.133042
C	0.95463100	-1.31539800	0.06660200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.093979

H	1.03250800	-2.16636300	-0.63046900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-325.142234
H	1.46360400	-1.65929800	0.98120000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-325.135702
C	1.63499500	-0.05822800	-0.49563200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-325.134758
H	1.39292300	0.06119700	-1.56060900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-325.173821
H	2.72308000	-0.16941600	-0.42477300		
C	1.13597800	1.16487300	0.28254500		
H	1.64958900	2.07852700	-0.03602100		
H	1.35963300	1.03258100	1.34995300		
C	-0.37899800	1.30257700	0.06707200		
H	-0.85046600	1.92542200	0.83697500		
H	-0.59405300	1.78957300	-0.89238600		
NH7 (2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline)					
C	-2.92568700	-1.39350100	-0.11222100	Zero-point correction=	0.266755 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.60285300	-1.77178600	-0.30596200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.278840
C	-0.55780600	-0.83412100	-0.20654800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.279784
C	-0.85956900	0.51626200	0.08993300	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.229707
C	-2.20126200	0.86397100	0.28770200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-522.017097
C	-3.23516700	-0.06629600	0.19172300	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-522.005013
H	-3.71367100	-2.13800900	-0.19375600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-522.004069
H	-1.36002500	-2.80619600	-0.54289100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-522.054146
H	-2.44556200	1.89461200	0.53101400		
H	-4.26465200	0.24071100	0.35186700		
C	1.88466500	-0.44860100	0.04070000		
N	0.75403600	-1.24871500	-0.44785400		
H	0.88811500	-2.24879400	-0.34587900		
C	3.14719100	-0.93441800	-0.68527600		
H	3.34523500	-1.99108100	-0.46227600		
H	4.02399200	-0.35982900	-0.36639400		
H	3.03452800	-0.83078600	-1.76925400		
C	2.06967400	-0.60213900	1.56670200		
H	2.32565600	-1.63885500	1.81807500		
H	2.87832900	0.04096900	1.93522800		
H	1.15376800	-0.34545300	2.10778000		
C	1.58144800	1.00894000	-0.35115900		
H	1.53520000	1.05783800	-1.44728700		
H	2.41076100	1.65378200	-0.03480000		
C	0.26053400	1.54556500	0.23019400		
H	0.41714700	1.73036800	1.30467300		
C	-0.07133700	2.90325300	-0.41408500		
H	-0.93774200	3.38287700	0.05152700		
H	0.77740100	3.59010400	-0.31012200		
H	-0.28572100	2.78598400	-1.48274400		
NH7-RAD (2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline)					
C	-2.91121000	-1.43253700	-0.09731500	Zero-point correction=	0.253253 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.58778800	-1.82467800	-0.14167600	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.265199
C	-0.52169000	-0.87376400	-0.04004000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.266143
C	-0.85853400	0.52196700	0.11281700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.215477
C	-2.20205700	0.87944100	0.15781700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-521.389339
C	-3.22511500	-0.07309700	0.05460100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-521.377394
H	-3.70485700	-2.17047200	-0.17756000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-521.376450
H	-1.30267200	-2.86583300	-0.25647900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-521.427116
H	-2.47558800	1.92386800	0.27503600		
H	-4.26273600	0.24732900	0.09189900		
C	1.86622300	-0.46970200	-0.00957900		
N	0.72325800	-1.37984700	-0.08748500		

C	2.95626100	-1.04818000	-0.93062000		
H	3.19839600	-2.07359000	-0.63412100		
H	3.86916500	-0.44224600	-0.88263100		
H	2.61128800	-1.06945100	-1.97022300		
C	2.37392200	-0.51283400	1.45247600		
H	2.59440900	-1.54546800	1.73981100		
H	3.28995000	0.08141200	1.55456600		
H	1.62876800	-0.12326300	2.15356400		
C	1.52208100	0.96893400	-0.44858300		
H	1.34910400	0.96956800	-1.53452800		
H	2.37889900	1.62974400	-0.26483800		
C	0.27078000	1.52893700	0.24554800		
H	0.49855100	1.63204200	1.31877800		
C	-0.06696600	2.93209700	-0.28073200		
H	-0.87471400	3.40629500	0.28622800		
H	0.81147800	3.58261800	-0.20091600		
H	-0.36768200	2.89685800	-1.33447300		
NH8 (Carbazole)					
C	-3.04482400	1.15323100	0.00002700	Zero-point correction=	0.176915 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-3.42877100	-0.19947300	0.00004000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.185854
C	-2.48176900	-1.22121100	0.00001200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.186798
C	-1.13377600	-0.85564700	-0.00002600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.142943
C	-0.72514800	0.50512800	-0.00002200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-517.293694
C	-1.69923500	1.51078900	-0.00000600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-517.284755
H	-3.80830500	1.92594300	0.00004300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-517.283811
H	-4.48486600	-0.45544800	0.00007200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-517.327667
H	-2.78362100	-2.26530300	0.00002400		
H	-1.40841800	2.55816500	-0.00001300		
C	1.13376900	-0.85564300	-0.00004800		
C	2.48176000	-1.22121000	0.00002500		
C	3.42876500	-0.19947400	0.00004800		
C	3.04482400	1.15323200	0.00001900		
C	1.69923600	1.51079400	-0.00002300		
C	0.72515300	0.50513100	-0.00004700		
H	2.78361600	-2.26530300	0.00006800		
H	4.48485900	-0.45545200	0.00010700		
H	3.80830800	1.92594000	0.00003800		
H	1.40842000	2.55817000	-0.00003600		
N	0.00000600	-1.65408100	-0.00005400		
H	0.00006200	-2.66201600	0.00007800		
NH8-RAD (Carbazole)					
C	3.06282800	-1.09543700	-0.00013600	Zero-point correction=	0.163538 (Hartree/Particle)
C	3.41903500	0.25884100	-0.00014000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.172146
C	2.43928900	1.25569300	-0.00009200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.173090
C	1.09309600	0.86574600	-0.00004000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.129121
C	0.73212000	-0.52076400	-0.00004000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-516.660152
C	1.71214200	-1.49750600	-0.00008700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-516.651544
H	3.84173200	-1.85295200	-0.00017000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-516.650600
H	4.46938300	0.53555900	-0.00018000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-516.694569
H	2.69816700	2.31004300	-0.00009100		
H	1.45949800	-2.55485100	-0.00008900		
C	-1.09309500	0.86574700	0.00005600		
C	-2.43928900	1.25569200	0.00011500		
C	-3.41903400	0.25883900	0.00014400		
C	-3.06282600	-1.09543800	0.00012100		

C	-1.71214000	-1.49750600	0.00005700	
C	-0.73211900	-0.52076500	0.00002400	
H	-2.69816800	2.31004200	0.00013800	
H	-4.46938300	0.53555600	0.00018600	
H	-3.84172900	-1.85295500	0.00015200	
H	-1.45949500	-2.55485200	0.00003400	
N	-0.00000600	1.70365200	0.00001700	
NH9 (Dimethyl-phenothioazine)				
C	-3.56904200	0.54877600	0.38559800	Zero-point correction= 0.234521 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-2.35176200	1.14757900	0.04362900	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.248035
C	-1.23660800	0.31886200	-0.20077000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.248979
C	-1.36595000	-1.07589400	-0.09037700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.194895
C	-2.58084800	-1.64556100	0.28998900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -994.043891
C	-3.69123700	-0.83305900	0.51677400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -994.030378
C	1.36604800	-1.07585400	-0.09045100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -994.029433
C	1.23657900	0.31886800	-0.20082500	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -994.083518
C	2.35164400	1.14768100	0.04369600	
C	3.56898800	0.54897400	0.38562800	
C	3.69133500	-0.83286400	0.51665100	
C	2.58101600	-1.64545200	0.28981500	
H	-4.43141600	1.18690500	0.56241200	
H	-2.65447700	-2.72469700	0.39018000	
H	-4.64306800	-1.27596800	0.79441500	
H	4.43128600	1.18717900	0.56253000	
H	4.64321200	-1.27570600	0.79423800	
H	2.65473000	-2.72458600	0.38994900	
S	0.00011700	-2.13011100	-0.55029100	
N	-0.00003400	0.88222000	-0.56158200	
H	-0.00013700	1.89007900	-0.59883500	
C	2.23697000	2.64950400	-0.07314400	
H	1.95366200	2.96751900	-1.08659500	
H	1.48944400	3.06210300	0.61987500	
H	3.19180400	3.12915000	0.15923200	
C	-2.23725800	2.64940400	-0.07341200	
H	-1.48993400	3.06219600	0.61970700	
H	-1.95377700	2.96730500	-1.08684700	
H	-3.19220900	3.12896200	0.15867300	
NH9-RAD (Dimethyl-phenothioazine)				
C	-3.62218400	0.57774600	-0.00005900	Zero-point correction= 0.220977 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-2.36923600	1.17254800	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.234451
C	-1.19363700	0.34741200	0.00002300	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.235395
C	-1.37479100	-1.06830300	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.180276
C	-2.65196100	-1.63854000	-0.00006800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -993.434728
C	-3.77250000	-0.81801800	-0.00009900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -993.421254
C	1.37479400	-1.06830200	-0.00000500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -993.420310
C	1.19364000	0.34741200	0.00002800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -993.475429
C	2.36923900	1.17254900	0.00000300	
C	3.62218600	0.57774600	-0.00004700	
C	3.77250200	-0.81801900	-0.00010000	
C	2.65196200	-1.63854100	-0.00008600	
H	-4.50678200	1.20956300	-0.00007900	
H	-2.76123100	-2.72005300	-0.00009200	
H	-4.76529500	-1.25868200	-0.00015300	
H	4.50678400	1.20956200	-0.00005900	
H	4.76529700	-1.25868300	-0.00015900	

H	2.76123200	-2.72005400	-0.00012500	
S	-0.00000400	-2.16983300	0.00014100	
N	0.00000300	0.99466000	0.00004500	
C	2.21730000	2.67093800	0.00003100	
H	1.65505200	3.01219300	-0.87608800	
H	1.65471200	3.01212400	0.87595000	
H	3.19670900	3.15950700	0.00023300	
C	-2.21730300	2.67093900	0.00002800	
H	-1.65488100	3.01214600	0.87605000	
H	-1.65489400	3.01218100	-0.87598900	
H	-3.19671500	3.15950200	0.00004300	
OH1 (4-Chlorophenol)				
C	-0.95914800	-0.00196900	-0.00005700	Zero-point correction= 0.095213 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.27447200	1.21440700	-0.00005600	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.101902
C	1.11715800	1.22259900	0.00003000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.102846
C	1.82524000	0.01549900	0.00010600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.063968
C	1.13086000	-1.19839700	0.00011600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -766.965106
C	-0.26428400	-1.20868200	0.00003100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -766.958417
H	-0.82691600	2.14803200	-0.00012200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -766.957473
H	1.66910000	2.15691800	0.00003100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -766.996351
H	1.67606100	-2.14031200	0.00019200	
H	-0.80429600	-2.14948200	0.00003100	
O	3.18993200	0.08883100	0.00017800	
H	3.55663900	-0.80890300	0.00026700	
Cl	-2.72012700	-0.01045000	-0.00016800	
OH1-RAD (4-Chlorophenol)				
C	0.89814400	-0.00001700	-0.00004700	Zero-point correction= 0.082291 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.21253600	-1.23294800	-0.00002300	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.088716
C	-1.16322400	-1.23801500	0.00005600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.089660
C	-1.92490500	-0.00004700	0.00010000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.050468
C	-1.16328700	1.23800300	0.00013400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -766.341807
C	0.21247400	1.23290900	0.00003200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -766.335382
H	0.78004700	-2.15790300	-0.00007700	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -766.334438
H	-1.72612600	-2.16613700	0.00005600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -766.373630
H	-1.72621700	2.16606800	0.00025300	
H	0.77994600	2.15788600	0.00003100	
O	-3.18000200	0.00002800	0.00013200	
Cl	2.64129100	0.00003200	-0.00016600	
OH2 (2-Methoxyphenol)				
C	-1.39884200	-1.64679600	-0.00000400	Zero-point correction= 0.137945 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.01968800	-1.39699300	-0.00004700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.145938
C	0.43994500	-0.08336500	-0.00005600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.146882
C	-0.47423700	0.99047900	0.00001100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.105360
C	-1.84064700	0.73323300	0.00003900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -421.850977
C	-2.30208400	-0.58737200	0.00002100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -421.842983
H	-1.75411400	-2.67306600	-0.00001200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -421.842039
H	0.68009700	-2.22578700	-0.00012600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -421.883561
H	-2.52630500	1.57492100	0.00008700	
H	-3.37101400	-0.78041200	0.00004400	
O	-0.01700200	2.27538400	0.00003000	
H	0.95502800	2.22778900	-0.00022800	
O	1.75761500	0.31661700	-0.00012500	
C	2.76059400	-0.68634800	0.00010800	
H	2.69233900	-1.31841200	-0.89477900	
H	3.71676100	-0.15985900	0.00021600	

H	2.69204500	-1.31821400	0.89513200		
OH2-RAD (2-Methoxyphenol)					
C	-1.25500600	-1.67836300	0.00017500	Zero-point correction=	0.125032 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.10448000	-1.34402100	0.00029800	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.132795
C	0.48994700	-0.00585300	0.00003400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.133739
C	-0.52140600	1.07005000	-0.00000800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.092069
C	-1.90817500	0.64603300	-0.00033100	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-421.227732
C	-2.25826100	-0.68324200	-0.00021100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-421.219969
H	-1.53897300	-2.72701900	0.00043100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-421.219025
H	0.84522600	-2.13611700	0.00073300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-421.260695
H	-2.64971500	1.43909300	-0.00053000		
H	-3.30399800	-0.97811200	-0.00036800		
O	-0.18814900	2.27434800	0.00032700		
O	1.75689300	0.43680600	0.00005800		
C	2.81530000	-0.51483500	-0.00030600		
H	2.77897000	-1.14754300	-0.89570400		
H	3.73676800	0.06842400	-0.00133100		
H	2.78049600	-1.14656800	0.89578700		
OH3 (4-Methoxy-2,3,6-trimethylphenol)					
C	-0.56322300	-1.30338200	-0.00000500	Zero-point correction=	0.220898 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.83422500	-1.37783700	-0.00000400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.234289
C	1.56617100	-0.18464200	0.00000100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.235233
C	0.92696300	1.06699700	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.180979
C	-0.47599700	1.12837100	-0.00000300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-539.714883
C	-1.21582000	-0.07052400	-0.00000600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-539.701493
H	-1.12883500	-2.22850300	-0.00000900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-539.700548
C	1.74907100	2.33480400	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-539.754802
H	2.81651700	2.11229100	-0.00005800		
H	1.52937700	2.95245700	-0.88042600		
H	1.52946400	2.95239900	0.88048800		
C	-1.18325500	2.46320100	-0.00000100		
H	-0.91028500	3.05944300	0.88038300		
H	-0.91038900	3.05939000	-0.88045600		
H	-2.26570600	2.33413200	0.00006500		
C	1.53951100	-2.71487800	-0.00000600		
H	2.17690100	-2.84978300	-0.88647200		
H	2.17693700	-2.84975200	0.88643800		
H	0.81801100	-3.53685000	0.00001700		
O	-2.58608800	0.06020200	-0.00000900		
C	-3.37261100	-1.11453100	0.00001400		
H	-4.41254700	-0.78070500	0.00002000		
H	-3.19133900	-1.72736900	-0.89414900		
H	-3.19132100	-1.72734600	0.89419000		
O	2.94582200	-0.18885300	0.00001200		
H	3.25513800	-1.10606700	0.00000900		
OH3-RAD (4-Methoxy-2,3,6-trimethylphenol)					
C	-0.54043600	-1.32543500	-0.00001500	Zero-point correction=	0.208600 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.83433000	-1.43230600	-0.00001000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.221609
C	1.65107700	-0.22335100	0.00000600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.222553
C	0.96766800	1.07243900	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.168493
C	-0.41443100	1.14866800	-0.00001900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-539.105724
C	-1.16870200	-0.06177400	-0.00001300	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-539.092714
H	-1.14104100	-2.22879400	-0.00002000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-539.091770
C	1.82678500	2.30674000	0.00001400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-539.145830
H	2.87935400	2.01962200	0.00036200		

H	1.63151800	2.93257700	-0.88092500	
H	1.63099100	2.93292600	0.88059000	
C	-1.12166200	2.48459000	-0.00001400	
H	-0.84250900	3.07647600	0.88062500	
H	-0.84169600	3.07690500	-0.88009600	
H	-2.20532200	2.36631300	-0.00052400	
C	1.54099000	-2.75625100	-0.00000500	
H	2.19504100	-2.84704400	-0.87498200	
H	2.19493200	-2.84709600	0.87504800	
H	0.83231400	-3.59029700	-0.00007200	
O	-2.51768400	0.08771400	-0.00000200	
C	-3.35409400	-1.06319900	0.00002400	
H	-4.37678400	-0.68295400	0.00003000	
H	-3.19225900	-1.67503900	-0.89550900	
H	-3.19223700	-1.67500700	0.89557500	
O	2.90500200	-0.30762800	0.00001400	
OH4 (2,2,5,7,8-Pentamethyl-chroman-6-ol)				
C	-2.09325100	-0.93717000	0.00825500	Zero-point correction= 0.313380 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.76964400	-1.40056500	0.07798100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.330360
C	0.27423900	-0.45722400	0.13728600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.331304
C	0.02085400	0.92219200	0.12359900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.270415
C	-1.30374100	1.38436000	0.02317300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -695.687233
C	-2.33972100	0.44628300	-0.02863800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -695.670254
C	2.67606500	-0.11708900	-0.06120100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -695.669309
O	1.55060200	-0.97384300	0.24180600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -695.730198
O	-3.62722000	0.93788800	-0.10670100	
H	-4.23920700	0.19710700	-0.22075200	
C	-1.61228800	2.86297700	-0.01906400	
H	-1.42234500	3.34411400	0.95053300	
H	-0.99057700	3.38224800	-0.75848900	
H	-2.65916700	3.03436000	-0.27299200	
C	-3.27480400	-1.88338900	-0.03119000	
H	-3.98682200	-1.67598100	0.78105000	
H	-3.82959800	-1.81472800	-0.97970000	
H	-2.97050300	-2.92485200	0.07835000	
C	-0.44578400	-2.87905200	0.09682200	
H	0.63186900	-3.03364200	0.04548500	
H	-0.80759700	-3.36336800	1.01352500	
H	-0.90410000	-3.40497000	-0.74945900	
C	2.79659100	0.03377000	-1.58529300	
H	3.64281600	0.68040100	-1.84505600	
H	2.95691400	-0.94644900	-2.04609200	
H	1.88956400	0.46454000	-2.01941200	
C	3.88570100	-0.86128400	0.50445600	
H	3.97362400	-1.85144700	0.04505200	
H	4.80753000	-0.30389800	0.30516100	
H	3.78379900	-0.99309300	1.58649600	
C	1.17051900	1.90531800	0.21019400	
H	1.31569800	2.39929400	-0.76225300	
H	0.92419300	2.71157200	0.91187700	
C	2.47054700	1.22654700	0.65247500	
H	3.32996700	1.88302200	0.47140200	
H	2.43518500	1.02936000	1.73129500	
OH4-RAD (2,2,5,7,8-Pentamethyl-chroman-6-ol)				
C	-2.14033100	-0.95823300	0.00387100	Zero-point correction= 0.301170 (Hartree/Particle)

C	-0.83168400	-1.39529500	0.06498000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.317699
C	0.22001800	-0.43161200	0.09384800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.318643
C	-0.01674800	0.96472700	0.09108800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.257780
C	-1.32308700	1.42315400	0.01637700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-695.080298
C	-2.43615800	0.47752900	-0.03401700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-695.063769
C	2.64221500	-0.12418800	-0.04742300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-695.062825
O	1.46628900	-0.96681100	0.14565000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-695.123688
O	-3.62244100	0.89000300	-0.10271400		
C	-1.65197100	2.89079600	-0.00539500		
H	-1.37237600	3.38182900	0.93730600		
H	-1.11642000	3.41538800	-0.80711200		
H	-2.72543800	3.01851400	-0.15169100		
C	-3.31811300	-1.89816500	-0.03687600		
H	-4.23934600	-1.31566700	-0.08231000		
H	-3.28106400	-2.55883200	-0.91224900		
H	-3.35514900	-2.54108100	0.85148200		
C	-0.44840600	-2.85620700	0.09525900		
H	0.20543800	-3.10892500	-0.74763100		
H	0.11453100	-3.09732600	1.00486000		
H	-1.32560200	-3.50337400	0.05468500		
C	2.86014300	0.04095300	-1.55740600		
H	3.74777800	0.65371900	-1.75083000		
H	3.00820500	-0.93797600	-2.02403500		
H	2.00191800	0.51816100	-2.03952500		
C	3.78360200	-0.91886500	0.58513700		
H	3.87303400	-1.90238500	0.11289400		
H	4.73251400	-0.38660000	0.45943400		
H	3.60536100	-1.06534900	1.65516600		
C	1.15591600	1.91908300	0.18041100		
H	1.33933500	2.38518000	-0.79843100		
H	0.91201600	2.74553000	0.85767000		
C	2.42010100	1.20983000	0.67464200		
H	3.30067700	1.84864200	0.54105000		
H	2.33081600	1.00398500	1.74879700		
OH5 (2,3,5-Trimethyl-chroman-4-ol)					
C	-1.74780100	-0.64504700	0.01900000	Zero-point correction=	0.257870 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.55589700	-1.38728400	0.01859500	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.271960
C	0.66876600	-0.69479800	0.00750600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.272904
C	0.72669400	0.70713600	0.00055500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.217891
C	-0.46857400	1.44772900	-0.02852200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-617.107535
C	-1.68616800	0.75881000	-0.01621900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-617.093445
O	1.80950300	-1.47574300	0.03097300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-617.092501
O	-2.83673800	1.52074500	-0.02736900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-617.147514
H	-3.60179100	0.93253000	-0.09829000		
C	-0.44934300	2.95830500	-0.06191400		
H	-0.09969600	3.38004200	0.89069500		
H	0.22382700	3.33437600	-0.84189900		
H	-1.44714800	3.35551000	-0.25225800		
C	-3.10791500	-1.30958200	0.05250300		
H	-3.71106600	-0.95558800	0.90137600		
H	-3.68611800	-1.11681200	-0.86432400		
H	-3.03272300	-2.39290200	0.15264800		
C	-0.56090500	-2.90080900	0.03339600		
H	-0.97452500	-3.29671900	0.97027400		
H	-1.16358300	-3.31164800	-0.78565400		

H	0.45317500	-3.28706800	-0.06930500	
C	2.06626300	1.42208800	0.02561500	
H	2.25507800	1.88889900	-0.95326700	
H	2.03687100	2.24873000	0.74587700	
C	3.21867700	0.47079100	0.36781900	
H	3.23520000	0.26056600	1.44438400	
H	4.18538500	0.91629500	0.10450500	
C	3.01928800	-0.84141900	-0.37643000	
H	3.81094600	-1.56450400	-0.16092900	
H	2.99553100	-0.66724200	-1.46408100	
OH5-RAD (2,3,5-Trimethyl-chroman-4-ol)				
C	-1.81898100	-0.57072700	0.02268200	Zero-point correction= 0.245440 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.67395100	-1.34532400	0.01219200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.259211
C	0.59483700	-0.69810100	-0.02452400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.260155
C	0.73505500	0.71472200	-0.02766200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.204038
C	-0.40383800	1.50425000	-0.03803100	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -616.500034
C	-1.72977400	0.88915000	-0.01578200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -616.486263
O	1.67018000	-1.53122700	-0.03484300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -616.485319
O	-2.76735500	1.59990600	-0.02237300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -616.541437
C	-0.33364200	3.00677100	-0.05780700	
H	0.10735300	3.40357400	0.86740000	
H	0.28421700	3.37402300	-0.88715200	
H	-1.34096300	3.41375600	-0.15660000	
C	-3.19245300	-1.18302200	0.06240200	
H	-3.30981200	-1.85322200	0.92353800	
H	-3.94258500	-0.39322000	0.12129000	
H	-3.39128100	-1.78435100	-0.83528400	
C	-0.74980100	-2.85488600	0.04061400	
H	-1.06592800	-3.21501500	1.02883700	
H	-1.48595700	-3.22417100	-0.68187600	
H	0.21513100	-3.30893400	-0.18615900	
C	2.12027000	1.33605300	-0.00696400	
H	2.36627300	1.73030100	-1.00455400	
H	2.12947200	2.20012400	0.66666300	
C	3.18757300	0.32337500	0.41945700	
H	3.12388500	0.12939600	1.49733700	
H	4.19509700	0.70202500	0.21265300	
C	2.96205200	-0.97913000	-0.32872100	
H	3.67154300	-1.75860700	-0.04080000	
H	3.03687000	-0.82390800	-1.41469900	
OH6 (Ubiquinol-2)				
C	-1.94476400	-0.94852100	0.53390300	Zero-point correction= 0.439420 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.25656600	0.10468500	1.15198700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.466412
C	-1.67643700	1.43174600	0.92826200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.467356
C	-2.79460900	1.66657600	0.11402800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.379805
C	-3.48607900	0.60616200	-0.48510500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -1041.278069
C	-3.04756600	-0.70301200	-0.29224900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -1041.251077
O	-3.23447700	2.94702800	-0.10388000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -1041.250133
H	-3.95716800	2.86795500	-0.75298900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -1041.337684
O	-4.56831500	0.92973200	-1.29195200	
O	-3.68425200	-1.80492900	-0.84640000	
O	-1.54497200	-2.24336100	0.73990600	
H	-2.20432000	-2.79742200	0.28346700	
C	-5.84104100	0.52113400	-0.76354400	
H	-5.89117000	-0.56789800	-0.67162600	

H	-6.01956600	0.97943400	0.21685900	
H	-6.59261100	0.86986600	-1.47567400	
C	-3.54397600	-1.91021900	-2.27314500	
H	-4.00840600	-1.05468900	-2.77247100	
H	-2.48579400	-1.96827800	-2.55577800	
H	-4.05402000	-2.83215600	-2.56211600	
C	-0.97197200	2.60986100	1.56398200	
H	-1.34477000	3.54820500	1.14979700	
H	-1.13437900	2.63839000	2.64974900	
H	0.11067300	2.57278200	1.40129800	
C	7.28230400	0.44126700	-1.96014300	
H	7.60065300	1.38716300	-2.42137400	
H	8.16102300	0.04379500	-1.43229600	
H	7.02521400	-0.25685500	-2.76315900	
C	1.81829100	-2.71095100	1.64489200	
H	1.94742900	-3.48479300	0.87618300	
H	2.55493300	-2.92891400	2.43151000	
H	0.81898300	-2.83283900	2.06504500	
C	6.42417500	1.61556800	0.11941500	
H	5.58458100	1.75051300	0.80499100	
H	7.28436500	1.26522900	0.70704000	
H	6.70046900	2.60485700	-0.27197700	
C	3.33155700	-1.25424300	0.23750500	
H	4.16938600	-1.59029100	0.86835400	
H	3.27558700	-2.00240600	-0.56971600	
C	6.12760200	0.65891000	-1.01011300	
C	2.05205500	-1.33986900	1.05282700	
C	-0.05275700	-0.22778700	2.02043700	
H	-0.23838100	-1.17214200	2.53616600	
H	0.04895800	0.53859700	2.79940800	
C	3.69878000	0.10925100	-0.37544200	
H	3.78882500	0.85561300	0.42046500	
H	2.87131300	0.44185200	-1.01941600	
C	1.23536400	-0.28981800	1.22602900	
H	1.49781500	0.64982300	0.74322000	
C	4.95579600	0.03310900	-1.20102300	
H	4.88555800	-0.63624600	-2.06138700	
OH6-RAD (Ubiquinol-2)				
C	1.83129200	0.42539400	0.55907200	Zero-point correction= 0.426518 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.44121400	-0.94144500	0.50002500	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.453228
C	2.29783500	-1.86205200	-0.08485800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.454172
C	3.59935400	-1.44318600	-0.60531400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.365834
C	3.96819900	-0.02162500	-0.48837000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -1040.658272
C	3.07625500	0.88735300	0.06394900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -1040.631562
O	4.39517300	-2.25428900	-1.12942400	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -1040.630618
O	5.18870500	0.24706100	-0.98469600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -1040.718955
O	3.38067600	2.22875000	0.17830500	
O	1.03025900	1.37602100	1.10268500	
H	0.12063400	1.02120700	1.17247100	
C	5.92433300	1.41112100	-0.60222500	
H	6.95348000	1.20101700	-0.90269900	
H	5.56686900	2.30663300	-1.11787900	
H	5.87611400	1.57545600	0.47751500	
C	2.72638600	3.07035000	-0.77501000	
H	2.99229300	2.78474600	-1.80170700	

H	1.63905400	3.03541900	-0.65338700	
H	3.08077300	4.08494300	-0.57681100	
C	1.97901900	-3.33118300	-0.19943800	
H	2.79338900	-3.82871300	-0.72836400	
H	1.87037200	-3.80433400	0.78518600	
H	1.04636900	-3.50719600	-0.75016500	
C	-7.49732100	1.09590800	-1.63310900	
H	-7.29474100	1.34373800	-2.68463100	
H	-8.47269700	0.58942400	-1.61692200	
H	-7.59308500	2.03317700	-1.07603500	
C	-2.20534100	-0.08128800	2.83458000	
H	-2.98921700	-0.78123300	3.15197600	
H	-1.27935300	-0.38738200	3.32730500	
H	-2.48834200	0.90411900	3.22610200	
C	-6.23731300	-1.10097700	-1.79457000	
H	-5.44338400	-1.72653200	-1.38029500	
H	-7.16863100	-1.68391800	-1.77449100	
H	-6.00702400	-0.92417900	-2.85435400	
C	-3.24034000	0.63456300	0.60166300	
H	-3.38284700	1.64638400	1.01007200	
H	-2.99033000	0.75561600	-0.45855300	
C	-6.41425700	0.20870700	-1.06531000	
C	-2.09520600	-0.04470100	1.32742300	
C	0.12043000	-1.35335900	1.14015400	
H	0.20096700	-1.25268000	2.23041100	
H	-0.03927500	-2.42048800	0.95419700	
C	-4.58644300	-0.12910400	0.70582900	
H	-4.85039500	-0.24518500	1.76686400	
H	-4.44933100	-1.14036600	0.30908200	
C	-1.08431600	-0.59292400	0.62325400	
H	-1.12965800	-0.51406300	-0.46421400	
C	-5.70135800	0.59806200	0.00319600	
H	-5.93504300	1.57635500	0.42870500	
OH7 (2,2,6,7-Tetramethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzofuran-5-ol)				
C	0.27407700	0.37380100	0.10329800	Zero-point correction= 0.255992 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.31590400	-1.01928600	0.10882100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.270261
C	-0.86196100	-1.74794700	0.05917500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.271205
C	-2.07305600	-1.04868100	0.00489200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.215952
C	-2.11865600	0.35826000	0.00371900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -617.113180
C	-0.91563000	1.09962100	0.04904300	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -617.098911
C	2.52333800	-0.10601400	-0.02333300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -617.097966
H	-0.87801500	-2.83359400	0.06165900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -617.153219
O	-3.21580100	-1.81485400	-0.04564400	
H	-3.98743800	-1.23219900	-0.09315100	
O	1.52052900	0.94990900	0.16365000	
C	-3.46939800	1.03934100	-0.05186800	
H	-4.01918200	0.79006200	-0.97193300	
H	-4.10681800	0.75430000	0.79839000	
H	-3.37960600	2.12637100	-0.02480800	
C	-0.87732300	2.61052800	0.04022800	
H	-1.37255500	3.02757900	-0.84554500	
H	-1.37294600	3.03860900	0.92101700	
H	0.15735900	2.95993600	0.03948900	
C	3.63104000	0.14877300	0.99331900	
H	4.41541000	-0.61168200	0.90485900	

H	4.08550600	1.13195600	0.83161300	
H	3.23095600	0.11795600	2.01190200	
C	3.02932800	0.00575600	-1.46411400	
H	3.44599400	1.00167000	-1.64631100	
H	3.80891500	-0.73970400	-1.66056800	
H	2.20925500	-0.15931600	-2.17135100	
C	1.75889800	-1.44542900	0.21332700	
H	1.98200300	-1.86036000	1.20606000	
H	2.04397800	-2.20436000	-0.52440500	
OH7-RAD (2,2,6,7-Tetramethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzofuran-5-ol)				
C	0.22013200	0.34943400	-0.07187400	Zero-point correction= 0.243633 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.30354700	-1.06200600	-0.07953800	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.257578
C	-0.83845900	-1.81055000	-0.04251700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.258522
C	-2.13490000	-1.15224600	0.00106000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.202587
C	-2.16655300	0.32014600	-0.00139500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -616.504686
C	-0.99257200	1.06611600	-0.03634800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -616.490741
C	2.49311800	-0.07518900	0.01700100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -616.489797
H	-0.83563600	-2.89642000	-0.04837400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -616.545732
O	-3.19305400	-1.82759900	0.03695000	
O	1.43101900	0.94828700	-0.10408500	
C	-3.51479400	0.98245100	0.04181000	
H	-4.29516100	0.22001100	0.05689700	
H	-3.62309400	1.61644800	0.93222300	
H	-3.67081300	1.63332800	-0.82888600	
C	-0.98944300	2.57577500	-0.03321100	
H	-1.50719400	2.97606800	-0.91390200	
H	-1.50872000	2.97233200	0.84791000	
H	0.03014100	2.96699800	-0.03260100	
C	3.08515600	0.08007000	1.41793600	
H	3.90915200	-0.62754700	1.56354900	
H	3.46894500	1.09481100	1.56303500	
H	2.32491300	-0.11498600	2.18184700	
C	3.51125700	0.22316200	-1.07774800	
H	3.93280300	1.22576100	-0.95278700	
H	4.33106000	-0.50282300	-1.03951500	
H	3.04364700	0.16489900	-2.06586800	
C	1.76255000	-1.43867100	-0.16648500	
H	2.06265800	-2.15954000	0.60183300	
H	1.99935400	-1.88579000	-1.14042700	
OH8 (1-Hydroxynaphthalene)				
C	2.74233800	0.29344900	0.00000000	Zero-point correction= 0.151989 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.77705500	1.27541800	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.159962
C	0.39511100	0.94532900	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.160906
C	0.02833200	-0.43912400	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.119441
C	1.04183600	-1.43209700	0.00000200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -460.957096
C	2.37176400	-1.07249200	0.00000200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -460.949123
H	-0.33087800	2.98902800	0.00000300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -460.948179
H	3.79463900	0.56549900	0.00000000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -460.989645
H	2.06025600	2.32543600	-0.00000100	
C	-0.61977500	1.94138700	0.00000200	
C	-1.36049500	-0.77166200	-0.00000300	
H	0.74978600	-2.47664900	0.00000400	
H	3.14170000	-1.83934100	0.00000400	
C	-2.32450600	0.21540700	-0.00000400	
C	-1.94612500	1.57868200	0.00000200	

H	-3.37897400	-0.05525900	-0.00001300	
H	-2.72197800	2.33949600	0.00000200	
O	-1.66479000	-2.10611100	-0.00001600	
H	-2.62944200	-2.20509600	0.00013000	
OH8-RAD (1-Hydroxynaphthalene)				
C	2.71201200	-0.39611500	0.00000000	Zero-point correction= 0.139197 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.69000700	-1.33135300	0.00000100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.146932
C	0.33648100	-0.91804200	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.147876
C	0.04446000	0.47588100	0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.106022
C	1.09054800	1.40619200	0.00000000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -460.343385
C	2.41338300	0.97785200	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -460.335650
H	-0.50444200	-2.91991500	0.00000200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -460.334705
H	3.74757100	-0.72502900	-0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -460.376560
H	1.91812100	-2.39454700	0.00000100	
C	-0.73854400	-1.85840100	0.00000000	
C	-1.36373100	0.93785300	0.00000000	
H	0.83581700	2.46123700	-0.00000100	
H	3.21991000	1.70587900	-0.00000100	
C	-2.39188900	-0.08857800	0.00000000	
C	-2.07225400	-1.43713600	-0.00000100	
H	-3.42158900	0.25516100	-0.00000200	
H	-2.86466000	-2.18119300	-0.00000200	
O	-1.65669700	2.14868500	0.00000000	
OH9 (4,4'-Dihydroxybiphenyl)				
C	0.74171400	0.00219900	-0.00277000	Zero-point correction= 0.189907 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.46944600	1.14371400	-0.38646900	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.201197
C	2.85969100	1.15940100	-0.38632100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.202141
C	3.56819900	0.01639500	-0.00169600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.152477
C	2.86875300	-1.13188000	0.38130000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -613.548341
C	1.47525100	-1.13164900	0.38082800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -613.537052
H	0.93434000	2.03003200	-0.71613500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -613.536108
H	3.41226000	2.04209900	-0.69284500	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -613.585772
H	3.41239500	-2.02260800	0.69253200	
H	0.94938900	-2.02370700	0.70958400	
O	4.93499200	0.08186200	-0.02057500	
H	5.29383600	-0.77459400	0.25903100	
C	-0.74170200	-0.00297300	-0.00245100	
C	-1.46987100	-1.14421300	-0.38621100	
C	-2.86011900	-1.15932900	-0.38619200	
C	-3.56820500	-0.01602500	-0.00167300	
C	-2.86833200	1.13195200	0.38142600	
C	-1.47482800	1.13115100	0.38108000	
H	-0.93512100	-2.03079300	-0.71574600	
H	-3.41301700	-2.04181200	-0.69274600	
H	-3.41163800	2.02289800	0.69262100	
H	-0.94862300	2.02295200	0.70997900	
O	-4.93502300	-0.08093500	-0.02070700	
H	-5.29354900	0.77566300	0.25887200	
OH9-RAD (4,4'-Dihydroxybiphenyl)				
C	0.67487400	0.00345800	-0.00219400	Zero-point correction= 0.177363 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.41050200	1.17407800	-0.29490200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.188342
C	2.79680800	1.18390400	-0.30048800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.189286
C	3.50392400	0.01164800	-0.00189500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.139449
C	2.80180300	-1.16290500	0.29585700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -612.928722
C	1.41236400	-1.16228800	0.29024400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -612.917743

H	0.88391300	2.08601500	-0.55773200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-612.916799
H	3.35196900	2.08453300	-0.54210400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-612.966637
H	3.34412000	-2.07411300	0.54145700		
H	0.89155100	-2.07737300	0.55346800		
O	4.86402900	0.07727400	-0.01733300		
H	5.23001400	-0.79478400	0.19941800		
C	-0.79253200	0.00077000	-0.00167200		
C	-1.52703700	-1.18524900	-0.29359400		
C	-2.89861400	-1.19979900	-0.29870600		
C	-3.67082300	-0.00454300	0.00188700		
C	-2.90224100	1.19357600	0.30003700		
C	-1.53053500	1.18421500	0.29145000		
H	-0.98422400	-2.08883200	-0.55571000		
H	-3.45682800	-2.09964900	-0.53946400		
H	-3.46302500	2.09157500	0.54168200		
H	-0.99039100	2.08999000	0.55123700		
O	-4.92378500	-0.00709400	0.00378300		
OH10 (1-Hydroxy-phenanthrene)					
C	3.18121600	0.92379500	0.00000300	Zero-point correction=	0.198938 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.63254200	-0.34645000	-0.00000700	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.209587
C	1.22340300	-0.53696000	-0.00000800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.210531
C	0.37065500	0.60560700	0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.162755
C	0.95945800	1.89315400	0.00002000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-614.555685
C	2.33245500	2.04382400	0.00001700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-614.545036
C	0.66620500	-1.85755800	-0.00001000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-614.544091
C	-1.07259600	0.39837400	-0.00000300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-614.591868
C	-1.58706400	-0.93295500	0.00001100		
C	-0.68141000	-2.04417800	0.00000700		
C	-2.98649500	-1.14163600	0.00001900		
H	-3.35866900	-2.16361800	0.00003300		
C	-3.86679100	-0.07840500	0.00000800		
C	-3.36573200	1.23702700	-0.00001900		
C	-2.00186000	1.46572400	-0.00002700		
H	1.34441100	-2.70329000	-0.00001900		
H	4.26209500	1.05241000	0.00001300		
H	0.33621500	2.77968100	0.00004900		
H	2.76771300	3.03939400	0.00003300		
H	-1.09744000	-3.04886700	0.00001200		
H	-4.93919900	-0.25371900	0.00001500		
H	-4.05276900	2.07901800	-0.00003800		
H	-1.64809000	2.49098500	-0.00006200		
O	3.40309300	-1.47870000	0.00000400		
H	4.33707700	-1.21857200	-0.00013000		
OH10-RAD (1-Hydroxy-phenanthrene)					
C	3.26398600	0.87363000	0.00000900	Zero-point correction=	0.186121 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.70976100	-0.46565900	0.00000500	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.196521
C	1.23510300	-0.58892400	0.00000200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.197465
C	0.41280200	0.56552000	-0.00000400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.149322
C	1.04102700	1.83870900	-0.00001100	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-613.940236
C	2.43894400	1.97858100	-0.00000700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-613.929836
C	0.66472100	-1.88265500	0.00000000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-613.928891
C	-1.03227200	0.40283900	-0.00000300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-613.977035
C	-1.57603100	-0.92082700	-0.00000500		
C	-0.69715400	-2.04473600	-0.00000600		
C	-2.98234100	-1.09954400	-0.00000200		

H	-3.37638000	-2.11291900	-0.00000500	
C	-3.83600900	-0.01757200	0.00000400	
C	-3.30508200	1.28868500	0.00000800	
C	-1.93828300	1.49094500	0.00000400	
H	1.34077000	-2.73094300	0.00000100	
H	4.34600000	0.95876200	0.00001700	
H	0.43735400	2.73919300	-0.00001700	
H	2.86597100	2.97809100	-0.00001300	
H	-1.13167700	-3.04149800	-0.00001000	
H	-4.91200000	-0.16706400	0.00000700	
H	-3.97504000	2.14404700	0.00001400	
H	-1.56476200	2.50925200	0.00000700	
O	3.44684100	-1.47385900	0.00000400	
SH1 (Benzenethiol)				
C	-2.29809900	0.00478300	-0.00000200	Zero-point correction= 0.099520 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.59134600	1.20781000	-0.00000700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.105857
C	-0.19607500	1.21104300	-0.00001100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.106801
C	0.50680200	-0.00013100	0.00001000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.068718
C	-0.20157800	-1.20942300	0.00002400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -630.334598
C	-1.59547600	-1.20179300	0.00000500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -630.328261
H	-3.38423600	0.00706000	-0.00000900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -630.327317
H	-2.12483400	2.15475200	-0.00001900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -630.365400
H	0.34052100	2.15612800	-0.00004900	
H	0.33599200	-2.15391900	0.00005200	
H	-2.13318700	-2.14623700	0.00000700	
S	2.29388800	-0.08360100	-0.00003500	
H	2.51816600	1.24609300	0.00045800	
SH1-RAD (Benzenethiol)				
C	-2.23648800	-0.00000400	0.00000200	Zero-point correction= 0.090843 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.53837900	1.21516300	-0.00000300	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.096402
C	-0.15032800	1.21989100	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.097346
C	0.57777900	-0.00000300	-0.00000500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.060371
C	-0.15031900	-1.21988600	-0.00000200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -629.719162
C	-1.53836900	-1.21516600	0.00000200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -629.713603
H	-3.32298400	-0.00001000	0.00000400	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -629.712659
H	-2.08437100	2.15437000	0.00000700	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -629.749634
H	0.40302500	2.15342200	0.00000200	
H	0.40303500	-2.15341600	-0.00000700	
H	-2.08435600	-2.15437400	0.00000400	
S	2.30639200	0.00000200	0.00000200	
SH2 (2-Methyl-benzenethiol)				
C	-2.39446300	0.01107700	-0.00083900	Zero-point correction= 0.127664 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.52670700	1.10271200	0.00332400	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.135369
C	-0.13494200	0.94177200	-0.00092000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.136313
C	0.37421200	-0.37337600	0.01663500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.095544
C	-0.49415800	-1.47161900	0.02067000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -669.623853
C	-1.87511300	-1.28262300	0.00121800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -669.616148
H	-3.46887800	0.17272100	-0.00622200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -669.615204
H	-1.93347100	2.11136500	-0.00267100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -669.655973
H	-0.08085200	-2.47567400	0.04807400	
H	-2.53787200	-2.14362900	0.00192900	
S	2.13345700	-0.73465900	-0.05397000	
H	2.55759100	0.21846000	0.80299500	
C	0.76816500	2.14949000	-0.02337400	
H	1.33578200	2.25598500	0.91178000	

H	1.50230100	2.08346700	-0.83519800		
H	0.18813000	3.06726000	-0.15745000		
SH2-RAD (2-Methyl-benzenethiol)					
C	-2.33947000	0.05923900	-0.00002900	Zero-point correction=	0.118628 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.44665900	1.13652000	-0.00005400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.125830
C	-0.06512300	0.94560100	-0.00001600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.126775
C	0.43481100	-0.39940900	0.00001600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.086070
C	-0.49227500	-1.47893000	0.00005800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-669.009507
C	-1.85973800	-1.25619700	0.00002800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-669.002304
H	-3.40955100	0.24901200	-0.00006100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-669.001360
H	-1.83813000	2.15071100	-0.00010300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-669.042065
H	-0.09420900	-2.48859000	0.00009300		
H	-2.55180200	-2.09344100	0.00004700		
S	2.12499500	-0.74818800	-0.00003800		
C	0.86212700	2.13265400	0.00004900		
H	1.51812100	2.12484500	0.87721200		
H	1.51967500	2.12375800	-0.87591800		
H	0.29393700	3.06783600	-0.00097300		
SH3 (3-Trifluoromethyl-benzenethiol)					
C	0.52266400	1.64679400	-0.02173700	Zero-point correction=	0.104359 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.65389000	0.25565900	-0.03590000	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.114258
C	-0.47156000	-0.56737500	-0.02722500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.115203
C	-1.75141300	0.00011000	-0.00298800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.067059
C	-1.88632400	1.39409800	0.01300700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-967.366658
C	-0.75271700	2.20663600	0.00267900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-967.356759
H	1.40486000	2.27731800	-0.03761600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-967.355815
H	-2.87311300	1.84836600	0.03053300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-967.403958
H	-0.87003400	3.28650300	0.01037600		
S	-3.14805900	-1.11272200	0.00163900		
H	-4.10654500	-0.16460100	0.02186400		
H	-0.34948400	-1.64536200	-0.04708100		
C	2.02730400	-0.36188500	-0.00135100		
F	2.04081900	-1.60029600	-0.54114200		
F	2.92833300	0.38613800	-0.67628700		
F	2.48775900	-0.47949700	1.26596200		
SH3-RAD (3-Trifluoromethyl-benzenethiol)					
C	0.44647600	1.62082500	-0.01673300	Zero-point correction=	0.095564 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.60639200	0.22653100	-0.02740200	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.104719
C	-0.50359600	-0.60677600	-0.02139500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.105663
C	-1.81250900	-0.05878000	-0.00279900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.058294
C	-1.95388000	1.35282200	0.01024300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-966.749531
C	-0.83537000	2.17709100	0.00250100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-966.740376
H	1.32207500	2.26215200	-0.03081900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-966.739432
H	-2.95390000	1.77390800	0.02414000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-966.786801
H	-0.95430800	3.25648900	0.00838500		
S	-3.19897100	-1.09150000	0.00256200		
H	-0.38516200	-1.68395300	-0.03600000		
C	1.99928500	-0.34919500	-0.00105700		
F	2.02139000	-1.64396900	-0.37474000		
F	2.82718600	0.33098900	-0.82585700		
F	2.53743000	-0.27809900	1.23761300		
SH4 (4-Amino-benzenethiol)					
C	-1.84845100	0.00000800	0.01294000	Zero-point correction=	0.116185 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.12890400	1.20792400	0.00464500	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.123935
C	0.26225700	1.20443100	-0.00750900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.124879

C	0.97673100	0.00003600	-0.00441600	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.083874
C	0.26227600	-1.20438500	-0.00758400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-685.671326
C	-1.12887600	-1.20790200	0.00461100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-685.663575
H	-1.66738300	2.15314100	0.00892700	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-685.662631
H	0.80191900	-2.14655900	-0.02242400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-685.703636
H	-1.66735000	-2.15311900	0.00902700		
S	2.77516700	0.00001700	-0.08019500		
H	3.02942900	-0.00057900	1.24989900		
H	0.80188500	2.14661300	-0.02229900		
N	-3.24117700	-0.00003900	0.08181900		
H	-3.69160300	0.83771400	-0.26449900		
H	-3.69153400	-0.83787800	-0.26436900		
SH4-RAD (4-Amino-benzenethiol)					
C	1.78813100	0.00000400	-0.00505800	Zero-point correction=	0.107649 (Hartree/Particle)
C	1.06751900	1.21794900	-0.00549400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.114675
C	-0.31187000	1.21417200	-0.00327400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.115619
C	-1.05748900	0.00000000	-0.00105000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.075565
C	-0.31186800	-1.21416700	-0.00329000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-685.063856
C	1.06752900	-1.21793800	-0.00549600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-685.056830
H	1.61308500	2.15901100	-0.00984100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-685.055886
H	-0.85793300	-2.15223400	-0.00086600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-685.095940
H	1.61310300	-2.15899500	-0.00979400		
S	-2.77461900	-0.00000400	0.00602200		
H	-0.85793600	2.15222700	-0.00087500		
N	3.16182000	-0.00000600	-0.04650100		
H	3.64957900	0.85072700	0.19624800		
H	3.64956200	-0.85075000	0.19625100		
SH5 (1-Naphthalenethiol)					
C	2.92350200	-0.67185300	-0.00000600	Zero-point correction=	0.146711 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.43281400	0.61331900	-0.00001100	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.155459
C	1.03468000	0.86733200	-0.00000400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.156403
C	0.12757200	-0.24526300	0.00000700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.112694
C	0.66919000	-1.55917500	0.00001600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-783.929808
C	2.03024300	-1.76867600	0.00001100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-783.921060
H	1.22207500	3.02488100	-0.00000900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-783.920116
H	3.99568700	-0.84809700	-0.00001200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-783.963826
H	3.11211000	1.46251800	-0.00002000		
C	0.52372100	2.19201600	-0.00000200		
C	-1.27971300	0.02305200	0.00000500		
H	-0.00036900	-2.41437700	0.00003500		
H	2.42092200	-2.78247600	0.00002000		
C	-1.73787100	1.32679700	0.00000500		
C	-0.83291900	2.41230300	0.00000600		
H	-2.80518700	1.53060400	0.00000300		
H	-1.22562900	3.42543000	0.00000800		
S	-2.40811100	-1.36901000	-0.00002000		
H	-3.53714600	-0.63342200	0.00013000		
SH5-RAD (1-Naphthalenethiol)					
C	2.93451900	-0.54929300	0.00000100	Zero-point correction=	0.137837 (Hartree/Particle)
C	2.37265100	0.70996600	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.145891
C	0.96386000	0.87647500	0.00000000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.146835
C	0.11751800	-0.27994500	-0.00000100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.103793
C	0.72518700	-1.55464900	-0.00000200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-783.318709
C	2.10183600	-1.68764500	0.00000100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-783.310656
H	1.03988900	3.03964300	-0.00000300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-783.309711

H	4.01462300	-0.66636900	0.00000200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-783.352753
H	3.00291400	1.59602500	0.00000000		
C	0.38209400	2.17377000	0.00000000		
C	-1.32813800	-0.09651200	-0.00000100		
H	0.08553300	-2.43055100	-0.00000100		
H	2.54607800	-2.67925100	0.00000000		
C	-1.83447400	1.22321000	-0.00000100		
C	-0.99256600	2.34056800	0.00000100		
H	-2.91189000	1.35155900	0.00000300		
H	-1.42146400	3.33861200	0.00000100		
S	-2.43816300	-1.40533400	0.00000100		
SH6 (4-Chloro-benzenethiol)					
C	-1.40102800	-0.00117300	-0.00000100	Zero-point correction=	0.089901 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.71189600	1.21087500	-0.00001300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.097448
C	0.68100700	1.20784800	-0.00002700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.098392
C	1.39111000	-0.00045800	-0.00001400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.056821
C	0.68314400	-1.20847800	0.00000400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-1089.939552
C	-0.71128900	-1.21159100	0.00000200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-1089.932005
H	-1.25798100	2.14820700	-0.00002300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-1089.931061
H	1.21257100	-2.15713900	0.00002600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-1089.972632
H	-1.25601800	-2.14979500	0.00001100		
S	3.17583200	0.08159600	0.00004100		
H	3.39798400	-1.24827400	-0.00043400		
H	1.21461400	2.15420700	-0.00006200		
Cl	-3.15945700	-0.00205200	0.00000700		
SH6-RAD (4-Chloro-benzenethiol)					
C	1.34454500	0.00000000	0.00002200	Zero-point correction=	0.081220 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.65911100	1.22183300	-0.00000700	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.087959
C	-0.72712300	1.21781300	-0.00004000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.088903
C	-1.45928000	0.00000000	-0.00008000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.048509
C	-0.72712300	-1.21781300	-0.00004000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-1089.324595
C	0.65911100	-1.22183300	-0.00000700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-1089.317856
H	1.21441400	2.15367400	0.00001500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-1089.316912
H	-1.27518200	-2.15435200	-0.00004400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-1089.357306
H	1.21441400	-2.15367400	0.00001500		
S	-3.18426900	0.00000000	0.00004300		
H	-1.27518200	2.15435200	-0.00004400		
Cl	3.09261100	0.00000000	0.00001700		
SH7 (4-Methyl-benzenethiol)					
C	-1.82906300	-0.00402300	-0.00915000	Zero-point correction=	0.127003 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.10476700	1.19591000	-0.00867300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.135281
C	0.28754800	1.20578700	-0.00221900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.136225
C	1.00060200	-0.00028000	0.00122100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.092588
C	0.29274100	-1.20653900	-0.00328600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-669.625040
C	-1.10230700	-1.19958000	-0.00909000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-669.616763
H	-1.63886700	2.14368800	-0.01469100	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-669.615819
H	0.82310000	-2.15526100	-0.00641400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-669.659455
H	-1.63322400	-2.14904200	-0.01529600		
S	2.78808900	0.08281500	0.00394200		
H	3.01138700	-1.24699800	0.01887000		
H	0.82015200	2.15320500	-0.00353500		
C	-3.33975800	-0.00265000	0.01284200		
H	-3.72590600	0.16282300	1.02767800		
H	-3.75008600	0.79158100	-0.62094900		
H	-3.74596600	-0.95678900	-0.33861400		

SH7-RAD (4-Methyl-benzenethiol)				
C	-1.76875300	0.00000400	-0.01142700	Zero-point correction= 0.118348 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-1.04744100	1.20870200	-0.01100600	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.125812
C	0.33819800	1.21604900	-0.00400200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.126756
C	1.07323300	0.00000000	0.00036400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.084331
C	0.33819400	-1.21604800	-0.00400200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -669.011344
C	-1.04744200	-1.20869700	-0.01100600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -669.003880
H	-1.59003500	2.15117800	-0.01772500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -669.002936
H	0.88610000	-2.15303500	-0.00529000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -669.045361
H	-1.59003900	-2.15117200	-0.01772600	
S	2.79797100	-0.00000200	0.00683100	
H	0.88610600	2.15303500	-0.00529000	
C	-3.27572900	-0.00000100	0.01475900	
H	-3.64796600	-0.00024800	1.04860900	
H	-3.68662700	0.88785700	-0.47677200	
H	-3.68662400	-0.88763600	-0.47718200	
SH8 (4-Methoxy-benzenethiol)				
C	1.38335400	-0.27705100	-0.00238300	Zero-point correction= 0.132306 (Hartree/Particle)
C	0.81343900	1.00145000	0.00200200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.141220
C	-0.57756600	1.13772400	0.00559200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.142164
C	-1.40973700	0.01685900	0.00465500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.097882
C	-0.82824100	-1.26062700	0.01561400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -744.824036
C	0.55202500	-1.40819300	0.00422100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -744.815122
H	1.43300900	1.89089700	0.00181200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -744.814178
H	-1.46500600	-2.13979800	0.03466100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -744.858460
H	1.01328100	-2.39085400	0.00821400	
S	-3.19889800	0.21616100	0.07208600	
H	-3.45864800	0.05567500	-1.24663600	
H	-1.01700400	2.13050100	0.00818500	
O	2.72264500	-0.52981200	-0.00883000	
C	3.61651900	0.57285300	-0.00753900	
H	3.49065500	1.19287900	0.88972800	
H	4.62000100	0.14376100	-0.01156800	
H	3.48615200	1.19876800	-0.90011500	
SH8-RAD (4-Methoxy-benzenethiol)				
C	-1.32257300	0.27631600	0.00004300	Zero-point correction= 0.123904 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.75688700	-1.01223300	0.00010700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.131998
C	0.62279300	-1.15248800	0.00007200	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.132942
C	1.48920400	-0.02708400	-0.00000700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.089967
C	0.88452400	1.26387200	0.00000400	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -744.213576
C	-0.48583800	1.41304700	0.00006900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -744.205481
H	-1.38511900	-1.89557600	0.00013600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -744.204537
H	1.52973200	2.13648800	0.00003400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -744.247513
H	-0.95128700	2.39366700	0.00015100	
S	3.19929200	-0.21739400	-0.00005700	
H	1.06533600	-2.14353000	0.00006700	
O	-2.65064000	0.53220400	-0.00005000	
C	-3.56430900	-0.56056300	-0.00007800	
H	-3.44248500	-1.18111000	0.89588500	
H	-4.55904600	-0.11318400	-0.00033400	
H	-3.44217200	-1.18128300	-0.89587700	
SH9 (4-Ethoxy-benzenethiol)				
C	-0.87512500	0.26634400	0.00027200	Zero-point correction= 0.160712 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.04728600	1.40042800	-0.00547000	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.171022
C	1.33364300	1.25888400	-0.01545500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.171967

C	1.92052200	-0.01602900	-0.00448800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.124156
C	1.09269400	-1.14018900	-0.00656000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-784.114991
C	-0.29877700	-1.00988300	-0.00376500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-784.104681
H	-0.51232700	2.38133500	-0.00959900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-784.103737
H	1.53616400	-2.13120300	-0.00953000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-784.151548
H	-0.91431100	-1.90194600	-0.00426300		
S	3.71062900	-0.20721000	-0.07026100		
H	3.96752500	-0.06042600	1.25066700		
H	1.96666000	2.14080800	-0.03328500		
C	-3.12035400	-0.59063000	0.00368200		
C	-4.52986900	-0.02542000	0.00763600		
H	-2.94558200	-1.21671200	0.89024100		
H	-2.94821700	-1.21108700	-0.88726600		
H	-5.26166700	-0.84033500	0.00636700		
H	-4.69603100	0.58999300	0.89725900		
H	-4.69878800	0.59523400	-0.87779600		
O	-2.21452400	0.51358300	0.00578400		
SH9-RAD (4-Ethoxy-benzenethiol)					
C	0.81509600	0.25965900	0.00043500	Zero-point correction=	0.152306 (Hartree/Particle)
C	-0.01518600	1.40170600	0.00032600	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.161800
C	-1.38649900	1.26237600	-0.00003000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.162744
C	-2.00036900	-0.02416900	-0.00022100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.116188
C	-1.14143600	-1.15537500	0.00009000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-783.504720
C	0.23904900	-1.02504400	0.00036200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-783.495226
H	0.45673300	2.37926900	0.00053300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-783.494282
H	-1.59083400	-2.14335800	0.00011000	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-783.540838
H	0.86066000	-1.91286100	0.00057200		
S	-3.71173800	-0.20255200	-0.00007800		
H	-2.02543200	2.13963200	-0.00010400		
C	3.06754800	-0.59074700	-0.00034400		
C	4.46805000	-0.00583200	0.00018900		
H	2.89746900	-1.21164700	-0.88992700		
H	2.89701400	-1.21168300	0.88908200		
H	5.20889300	-0.81229800	0.00035500		
H	4.62863500	0.61344600	-0.88756300		
H	4.62800400	0.61324100	0.88819600		
O	2.14364200	0.50645500	-0.00060700		

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